

ICAENS 2021 PROGRAM

Opening Ceramony - 1 NOV 2021 09:00-11:00

SPEAKERS

1	Josep M. Guerrero (Keynote Speaker)
2	Francesco Cottone (Keynote Speaker)
3	Carlos Coelho (Keynote Speaker)
4	Muhammad Sultan (Keynote Speaker)
5	Weidong Zhu (Keynote Speaker)
6	Mohammad Ashraf Gondal (Keynote Speaker)

Session 1.1		1 NOV 2021 11:00-12:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Covid-19 (Disease Management and Spread Control)	Samreen Diaz	Pakistan	Submission 1
Comparative Genomics of genes involved in cuticular wax biosynthesis in sunflower	Mahmood-Ur-Rahman Ansari, Hafiz Muhammad Ahmad	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 2
EFFECTS OF INPUT PARAMETERS ON MICROWAVE HYBRID HEATING BASED JOINING	Virinder Kumar, Shankar Sehgal	India, India	Submission 4
Assessing land use and land cover change detection using remote sensing and GIS in the Central Kashmir of Great Himalayas	Syed Rouhullah Ali	India	Submission 5
Generalized Complementarity problem with its corresponding variational inequality problem involving XOR-operation	Zahoor Rather	India	Submission 6
The Effect of Homogenization and Chemical Compositions of 6005 and 6082 Aluminium Alloys on The Cold Forming Process	Havva Demirpolat, Seracettin Akdi, Bülent Alkan	Turkey	Submission 7
Building and Cost Analysis of an Industrial Automation System using Industrial Robots and Programmable Logic Controller Integration	Enes Efe, Müciz Özcan, Hüseyin Haklı	Turkey	Submission 8
Kinetics and equilibrium study for the adsorption of synthetic dyes on olive stone-based activated carbon	Termoul Mourad, Attouti Salima, Benderdouch Nouredine, BENAOUA BESTANI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9
Metabolic Imbalance and Inflammatory Atherosclerosis Risk in Type 1 Diabetes: The Role of Ketosis as a Metabolic State	Walid Hassene Hamri, Mustapha Diaf, Noria Harir	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 12
Clinical Associations of dyslipidemia with the Risk of Atherosclerosis in Dysthyroid Type 1 Diabetic Patients	Walid Hassene Hamri, Mustapha Diaf, Noria Harir	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 13

Session 1.2		1 NOV 2021 11:00-12:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Optimization of Two hybrid Micro-Concentrator Photovoltaic Systems for car-roof application	Sarah Elhimer, Mariyam Ouaisa, Mariya Ouaisa	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 14
Effects of Fe/Si Loading Ratio onto Synthesis, Characterization and Catalytic Activity of Fe/SBA-15 Catalysts in the Liquid Phase Reaction	Veli Şimşek	Turkey	Submission 36
Wastewater treatment by a synthetic zeolite	Khedim Mohamed Amine, Feddag Ahmed, Chouaih Abdelkader	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 16
EVALUATION OF INHIBITORY ACTIVITY OF THREE LACTIC ACID BACTERIA STRAINS: BACTERIOCIN PRODUCTION	Zahia Benmouna Benamar, Fatiha Dalache, Halima Zadi Karam, Nour-Eddine Karam	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 17
Arabinogalactan – from tarragon wormwood (Artemisia Dracunculus)	Kulumkan Sartova, Aichurok Mazhitova	Kyrgyzstan, Kyrgyzstan	Submission 18
Study of adsorption of an organic pollutant from aqueous solutions on a biosorbent	Feddal Imene, Demmouche Safaa, Mimanne Gousseem, Taleb Safia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 19
Reinforcement of copper adsorption by the addition of humic acid on a microporous zeolite	Karima Menad, Ahmed Feddag, Houria Belhouari	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 20
Isomerization of light alkane nC4 on promoted tungstated zirconia	Zahira Mohamed Seghir, Mezouagh Amina, Mhammed Djennad	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 21
Experimental study of wettability alteration by emulsifiers in oil-based mud	Zineb Bazzine, Abdelmadjid Dobbi, Hamid Lebtahi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 22
Green synthesis of Copper nanoparticles using Allium cepa (onion) peels and its application to remove Disperse Yellow 3 dye	Dr. Shumaila Kiran, Abdul Ghaffar, Sofia Nosheen, Faiza Nourin	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 23

Session 1.3		1 NOV 2021 12:00-13:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Soil radioactivity, exposure dose, radiation hazard, environmental and health effects	Basim Almayahi	Malaysia	Submission 24
Self-powered UV photodetectors utilizing small organic semiconductors	Khaulah Sulaiman, Hanan Alzahrani	Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 25
Phytochemical composition and biological activities of extracts of Pistacia atlantica subsp. atlantica	Houari Benamar, Abderrazak Marouf, Malika Bennaceur	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 26
Green energy for synthetic textile wastewater treatment: Cost evaluation	Amel Belayachi, Benderdouche Noureddine, Hanane Belayachi, Sarra Bourahla, Cherif Haddad	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 27
Removal of CO ₂ from natural gas by membrane process	Amina Mezouagh, Zahira Mohammed Seghir, Belkacem Absar	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 28
MicroRNAs in molecular technology to address global disease bench to bedside research	Noor UL Ain Akram, Zainab Shahzor, Iram Mushtaq, Ayesha Ishtiaq, Khadam Hussain, Iram Murtaza	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 29
Control of a ball on a plate system using PID controller and Lead/Lag compensator	Hadoune Oussama, Benouaret Mohamed, Zeghida Abdennour, Saker Hichem	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 30
MAPPING SPATIAL VARIABILITY OF SOIL SALINITY IN A MODERN PALM GROVE (BISKRA SOUTH-EAST OF ALGERIA)	Rim Ouamane, Houcine Abdelhakim Reguieg Yssaad, Ali Masmoudi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 31
Effects of suspended and deposited TiO ₂ on performances of a solar photocatalytic system	Rafik Melki, Nadia Aicha Laoufi, Meriem Daimalah, Abdelkader Mouheb	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 32
Bi Ideals of Nearness Semirings	Özlem Tekin	Turkey	Submission 34

Session 1.4		1 NOV 2021 12:00-13:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Challenges in the production of titanium-based scaffolds bio-functionalized with hydroxyapatite by powder metallurgy technique	Mehmet Topuz, Burak Dikici, Mehmet Gavgali	Turkey	Submission 35
A Review paper on Optimized Reconfigurable Cell Array	Gnaneshwar Chary, Kakarla Hari Kishore	India, India, India, India, India	Submission 37
The Solutions to Matrix Equations and System of Fractional Differential Equations by Fixed-Point Approach	Muhammad Nazam, Muhammad Arshad, Choonkil Park	Pakistan, Pakistan, Korea	Submission 38
SYNTHESIS AND OPTIMISATION OF CINNAMOMUM ZEYLANCIUM LOADED PLGA NANOPARTICLES	Vinod Kumari, Aditi Sangal	India, India	Submission 39
Real Time IOT-Based Wearable Women Safety System	Raghuveera E,K Hari Kishore	India, India	Submission 40
BEHAVIOR OF IPN PERFOBOND CONNECTORS IN PUSH-OUT TEST	Boursas Farid, Boutagouga Djamel, Athmania Brahim	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 41
Study of clinical characteristics, frequency and genetic variants of ABCB4 gene in Pakistani obstetric cholestasis cases	Sabika Firasat, Nuzhat Noor, Kiran Afshan	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 42
Removal of two textiles dye from water by carbonated materials: Performance and mechanism	Samira Ziane, Fatima Boucif, Fatiha Bessaha, Imene Feddal, Nouria Mahrez, Amine Khelifa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 44
MHD ROTATING FLUID PAST A SEMI-INFINITE VERTICAL MOVING PLATE THROUGH A POROUS MEDIUM IN PRESENCE OF CHEMICAL REACTION: CORIOLIS FORCE AND WALL VELOCITY EFFECTS	Zohra Benharkat	Algeria	Submission 45
A strategy for energy-efficient control of temperature and humidity for agricultural applications using solar/heat energy	Muhammad Sultan	Pakistan	Mail Submission-1

Session 1.5		1 NOV 2021 13:00-14:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Variation in the composition of exopolysaccharides produced by <i>Lactiplantibacillus plantarum</i> strain Lbio28 based on the fermentation medium	Nadia Bachtarzi, Speciale Immacolata, Karima Kharroub, Cristina De Castro, Lorena Ruiz, Patricia Ruas Madiedo	Algeria, Italy, Algeria, Italy, Spain, Spain	Mail Submission-2
Development of Inventory Tracking System Supported by Android-Based QR Code Technology	Caglar Gurkan and Merih Palandoken	Turkey	Submission 714
Optimized Supercritical Fluid Extraction of Phytochemicals from Stevia Leaf Powder: Bioactive Compounds, Phenolic, Amino Acids Profiles and Comparison with Conventional Maceration Extraction	Kashif Ameer, Joong-Ho Kwon, Jong-Bang Eun, Mian Anjum Murtaz, Shahid Bashir, Ammar Ahmad Khan, Anees Ahmed Khalil	Pakistan, South Korea, South Korea, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Mail Submission-4
Biosensors for the detection of viruses and cancer cells- An emerging technology for point of care diagnostics	SZJ Zaidi, M.S Shahbaz, W.Gondal, S.Hassan	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Mail Submission-5
Numerical Modelling of a Nonplanar Strike Slip Fault and Associated Stress Distribution in Lithosphere Asthenosphere System	Subhash Chandra, Suma Debsarma	India, India	Submission 46
Elucidation of Pathway Crosstalks and Prospective Therapeutic Targets in Autism Spectrum Disorder	Umme Farwa, Sobia Khurshid, Syeda Marriam Bakhtiar	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 47
Biological control with essential oil of <i>Foeniculum vulgare</i> Mill	Djamila Hamada, Roumeissa Bekri, Aicha Medjahid, Romaissa kamaci, Hakim Belkhalifa, Nasrine Salhi, Segni Ladjel	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 50
INVESTIGATING MAJOR APOE SNPS TO DETERMINE THEIR ROLE IN CARDIOVASCULAR, NEURONAL AND DEFICIENCY DISORDERS	Shazina Pervaiz, Muhammad Qasim Khan, Syeda Marriam Bakhtiar	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 51
Photocatalytic degradation of cefaclor from aqueous solution, by a synthesized semiconductor	Meriem Daimalah, Nadia Aicha Laoufi, Rafik Melki, Abdelkader Mouheb	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 54
ROLE OF INSULIN RESISTANCE IN ONSET OF METABOLIC SYNDROME	Ifra Ghous, Zoha Ghous, Naveed Iqbal Soomro, Dr. Syeda Marriam Bakhtiar	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 55

Session 1.6		1 NOV 2021 13:00-14:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Isparta bölgesinin (GB Anadolu, Turkey) yeraltı yapılarının havadan manyetik verilerle incelenmesi	Ezgi Erbek	Turkey	Submission 56
Yapay Sinir Ağları İle Yerleşim Yerlerindeki Yeşil Alanların Belirlenmesi Ve Periyodik Değişimlerinin İzlenmesi	Osman Çoşkun, Cengiz Sertkaya	Turkey	Submission 57
Variability of phytochemical composition of twigs of <i>Retama sphaerocarpa</i> L. Boiss (Fabaceae) with seasons	Oumelkhir Moulay, Zohra Zemouri, Abderrezak Djabeur	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 58
Makine Öğrenmesi Metotları Kullanılarak Hepatit C Hastalığının Erken Teşhisinin Gerçekleştirilmesi	Nuh Yurduseven, Cengiz Sertkaya	Turkey	Submission 59
Yapay Sinir Ağları İle Buğday Tanelerinin Fiziksel Özelliklerine Göre Çeşidinin Tahmin Edilmesi	Mehmet Fatih Savran, Cengiz Sertkaya	Turkey	Submission 60
Yapay Sinir Ağı Kullanılarak Personelin Devamsızlık Tespitinin Gerçekleştirilmesi	Hayrünnisa Şenöz, Cengiz Sertkaya	Turkey	Submission 61
Comparative study of wastewater treatment by a local bentonite of "Maghnia" and hydrated aluminum sulfate for their reuse in irrigation	Khelladi Malika, ABAIDIA Meriem, Abdelkader Debab	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 63
Influence by Porosity on the Natural Frequencies for the Functionally Graded Plates Solar	Merdaci Slimane, Hadj Mostefa Adda and Zerrouki Otmane	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission-6
Virtualization of Clothing Thermal Comfort in 3D Simulations	Sertaç Güney	Turkey	Submission 64
Heat Transfer Analysis of Electric Discharge Machining Process using Finite Element Method	Hassan Fawwad Junejo, Tariq Saeed Khan	United Arab Emirates, United Arab Emirates	Submission 65

Session 1.7		1 NOV 2021 14:00-15:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Electrochemical detection of paracetamol molecules using reduced graphene oxide/silver composite modified carbon paste electrode (CPE) using plant extract.	Cylia Khelifi, Razika Aitout	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 66
Comparative study between structure with and without a fluid viscous damper under seismic excitation	Brahim Athamnia, Mohamed Zohair Kaab, Farid Boursas, Abdelhafid Ounis	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 67
The effect of the 6MV photon flattening filter on the contamination particles	Mustapha Assalmi, El Yamani Diaf	Morocco, Morocco	Submission 69
Cloning and Expression of Papase Gene in E. coli BL21 and its Effect on Dengue	Abdul Ghaffar, Bushra Munir, Umar Farooq	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 70
Design and realization of fully automatic egg incubator using PID controller.	Hadoune Oussama, Benouaret Mohamed	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 71
Giysi Endüstrisinde Üretim Performansının Tahmininde Yapay Sinir Ağlar	Cengiz Sertkaya, Samet AKÇAY	Turkey	Mail Submission-7
Identification and Analysis of microRNA-Disease Associations with Kernelized Bayesian Matrix Factorization	Ahmet Toprak, Esmâ Eryılmaz Dogan	Turkey	Mail Submission-8
Valorization of a biomaterial as coagulant in wastewater treatment	Khelladi Malika, ABAIDIA Meriem, Abdelkader Debab	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 72
FORECASTING COAL PRODUCTION VIA POLYNOMIAL REGRESSION ANALYSIS: THE SAMPLE OF EUROPEAN UNION	Ezgi Guler, Aslı Ergenekon Arslan, Süheyla Yerel Kandemir	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 74
Investigation of Disruptive Effect on Voltage Stability Caused by Line Contingency in Power Systems and Improvement of System Stability	Umut Emre Uzun, Nihat Pamuk, Sezai Taşkin	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 75

Session 1.8		1 NOV 2021 14:00-15:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Determination of antioxidant activity by chemical and electrochemical methods of extracts of <i>Launaea resedifolia</i> from the Algerian Sahara plant	Oumelkheir Rahim, Amina Bouguerra, Ali Douadi, Mohamed Hadjadj	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 76
Technical and Economic Study for PV project on Socotra Island, Yemen.	Saif Serag, Adil Echchleh	Morocco, Morocco	Submission 77
Progress of Blue Carbon Research in the Seagrass Meadows of Sungai Pulai Estuary (Johor, Malaysia)	Nur Hidayah, Natasha Arina, Chandran Raynusha, Nur Farah Ain Zainee, Nur Hazlin Hazrin-Chong, Mohammad Rozaimi	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 81
Investigating for Ion Selectivity and Water Repulsive Property of Carbazole Derived Compounds	Aysel Aydin Kocaeren	Turkey	Submission 84
Assessment of Site Selection Criteria for Medical Waste during COVID-19 Pandemic	Mehmet Ali Taş	Turkey	Mail Submission-9
The Use of H5P Module of LMS Moodle to Form Communicative Competence of Future Ship Engineers	Alona Yurzhenko, Olena Diahyleva and Mariia Masonkova	Ukraine, Ukraine, Ukraine	Submission 85
A Study on the Usability of Different Baking Techniques in Improving the Sensory Quality and Reducing Nutrient Loss of Some Traditional Bakery Products	Hüsnü Kasar, Süleyman Gökmen, Abdullah çağlar	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 86
Influence of the Nature of the Substrate's Material on the Characteristics of the Integrated Circuit	Amri Houda, ZAABAT Mourad	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 87
Ahmed Gövdesinin Aerodinamik Özelliklerinin Farklı Arka Yüzey Konfigürasyonları İçin Sayısal Olarak İncelenmesi	Cafer Kamaci, Kenan Kaya	Turkey	Submission 88
VARIABILITY OF NaI, D2, HeI, SiII, OI SPECTRAL LINES IN THE SPECTRUM HD 179218	Hemayil Adigozalzade	Azerbaija	Submission 89

Session 1.9		1 NOV 2021 15:00-16:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Impact Behavior of Aramid Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composites Produced By Hot Press-Prepreg Method	Ertan Kosedag, Recep Ekici	Turkey	Submission 90
MODELING OF WATER ADSORPTION ON LTA ZEOLITES	Amel Chaibi, Youcef Boucheffa, Nadia Bendjaballah-Lalaoui	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 91
Impacts of Floods on Bridges -A Review	Muhammad Abrar, Muhammad Usman Farooqi	Pakistan	Submission 94
A Study on Conservation of Church Buildings in Turkey: The Example of Yalova/Esenköy Azize Paraskevi Church	Tuba Nur Olgun	Turkey	Submission 95
Photo-oxidation study of industrial toxic dye by using mixed metal oxides doped with TiO ₂ under visible light and solar radiation.	Bessaha Hassiba, El Akeb Kheira and Bouraada Mohamed	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 96
Flow Regimes in Spiral Channel Packed with Steel Balls	Mustafa Yasin Gökaslan, Mustafa Özdemir and Lütfullah Kuddusi	Turkey	Submission 97
Classification of Facial Data with Capsule Networks	Ayşe Çoban and Fatih Özyurt	Turkey	Submission 98
Performance Test of GTA 5 Game With MSI Afterburner	Fatma Nur Canoğlu, Mahmut Melikşah Doğan, Mehmet Özel, Oğuzhan Şengüler and Fatih Başçıftçi	Turkey	Submission 99
Comparative Study of Impedance Spectroscopy Between Nickel-Metal Hydride and Lithium-ion Batteries	Salim Erol	Turkey	Submission 100
The Effect of Technology and Service on Learning Systems During the COVID-19 Pandemic	Arif Ullah and Özlem Batur Dinler Canan Batur Şahin	Malaysia, Turkey	Submission 101

Session 1.10		1 NOV 2021 15:00-16:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Effect of temperature on the properties of Co ₃ O ₄ / NiO / NiCo ₂ O ₄ / CoO obtained using the sol gel technique.	Leydi Julieta Cardenas Flechas, Luis Carlos Moreno Aldana and Miryam Rincón Joya	Columbia, Columbia, Columbia	Submission 102
Calculating of the basement of Eastern Pontides using Bouguer Gravity Data by NFG and inversion techniques	Ali Elmas	Turkey	Mail Submission-10
2D Modelling of Interface Topographies of the Central Anatolia Region	Ali Elmas	Turkey	Mail Submission-11
Bouguer gravite verileriyle Ankara ili ve civarındaki süreksizliklerin araştırılması	Ali Elmas	Turkey	Mail Submission-12
A Study On Structural Behaviour Of RC Buildings Pre-Designed According To Turkish Seismic Code Design Principles	Hakan Dilmaç	Turkey	Submission 104
Fruit peel extracts as a source of natural antioxidants for skin care formulations	Shazia Abrar, Ch. Moazzam Hassan and Maryam Habiba	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 105
Biodegradation of neonicotinoids insecticides by Actinobacteria isolated from activated sludge of a wastewater treatment plant located in eastern Algeria	Oumeima Boufercha, Irina Sousa Moreira, Paula Maria Lima Castro and Allaoueddine Boudemagh	Algeria, Algeria, Portugal, Portugal	Submission 108
Biodiversity of culturable Actinobacteria in activated sludge of wastewater treatment plants in Algeria	Oumeima Boufercha, Irina Sousa Moreira, Paula Maria Lima Castro and Allaoueddine Boudemagh	Algeria, Algeria, Portugal, Portugal	Submission 109
Dysregulation of circulating miRNAs promotes the pathogenesis of diabetes-induced cardiomyopathy	Muhammad Masoud, Uzair Ahmed, Usman Ashfaq, Muhammad Qasim and Saba Khaliq	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 110
Kalman Filter Implementation on Field-programmable Gate Array for Navigation Applications of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles	Metin Mert Deniz and Ufuk Sakarya	Turkey	Submission 111

Session 1.11		1 NOV 2021 16:00-17:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Kalman Filter Implementation on Field-programmable Gate Array for Navigation Applications of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles	Ferhat Yüksel and Ufuk Sakarya	Turkey	Submission 112
Delivery of Naproxen thiosemicarbazide/1,2,4-triazole Derived Chemotherapy Drugs Using Gold Nanoparticles	Cansu Ümran Tunç, Gizem Kurşunluoğlu, Pınar Atalay, M. İhsan Han and Ömer Aydın	Turkey	Submission 113
Double-diffusive convection in a shallow horizontal rectangular cavity uniformly heated and salted from below and filled with a non-Newtonian binary fluid: case of cooperating flows	Khadija Bihiche, Mohamed Lamsaadi and Mohammed Hasnaoui	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 114
A new public-key cryptosystem based on LCD codes	Selda Çalkavur	Turkey	Submission 115
Çarpan Hava Jetlerinde Farklı Parametrelerin Hız Sınır Tabakası Üzerindeki Etkisinin Simülasyonu	Burak Türkan	Turkey	Mail Submission 43
An examination of the studies on routing problems: A bibliometric analysis	Özlem Çomaklı Sökmen	Turkey	Submission 675
PARAMETRIC STUDY OF E129 RED DYE ADSORPTION ON ACTIVATED CARBON FROM EGGSHELLS	Amel Chaibi, Nadia Bendjaballah-Lalaoui, Youcef Boucheffa, Salim Boudiaf and Mohamed Amine Djilali	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 120
Clinical and Genetic Heterogeneity of Autosomal Recessive Primary Microcephaly Families in Pakistani Population	Muhammad Qasim	Pakistan,	Submission 121
Amplitude Responses at Flexural Eigenmodes in Dynamic Acoustic Force Measurement Using Multimodal Excitation Schemes	Cagri Yilmaz and Eyup Sabri Topal	Turkey	Submission 122
Ultrases ve Kaplama Ön İşlemlerinin Infrared Kurutulmuş Ayva Numunelerinde Kuruma Verimi ve Kalite Parametreleri Üzerine Etkisi	Tansu Yildirim	Turkey	Submission 123

Session 1.12		1 NOV 2021 16:00-17:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Electroosmotic flow transport of nanofluid through porous microchannel in presence of magnetic field	Amalendu Rana	India	Submission 126
Biolistic approach for transformation and overexpression of pathogenesis related gene 2 in bread wheat	Shazia Anwer Bukhari, Muhammad Numan, Ghulam Mustafa and Bushra Sadia	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 127
NESNELERİN İNTERNETİ İLE HIZ UYUMLU YEŞİL DALGA KORİDORU	Özgür Kart, Osman Çağrı Genç and Fatih Başçiftçi	Turkey	Submission 130
Recommender Systems based on RDF Graph Embeddings	Siham Eddamiri, Elmoukhtar Zemmouri and Asmaa Benghabrit	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 131
Geçmişten Günümüze Kablosuz Mobil İletişim Teknolojileri	Ramazan Akkurt	Turkey	Submission 135
Plastik Enjeksiyon Tezgâhlarında Vida Kırılmasının Akustik Emisyon Yöntemi ile Tespit edilmesi	Mustafa Timur and Halil Kılıç	Turkey	Submission 136
Molecular identification of Clerodendron yellow mosaic virus from Duranta repens and Clerodendrum inerme from Pakistan	Nazia Nahid	Turkey	Submission 138
Ağaçören/Aksaray bölgesindeki jeolojik yapıların jeofizik (manyetik) yorumu	Ezgi Erbek Kıran and Mustafa Nuri Dolmaz	Turkey	Submission 787
Taşkın Modelleme Yöntemlerinin İncelenmesi ve Karşılaştırılması	Vahdettin Demir and Neslihan Beden, Aslı ülke Keskin	Turkey	Submission 140
Inhibitory Potential and Drugability of Plant Phytochemicals against NS3/4A Protease of Hepatitis C Virus	Muhammad Yameen, Ghulam Mustafa, Abdul Ghaffar and Salaha Mahrosh	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 142

Session 1.13		1 NOV 2021 17:00-18:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Analysis of The Manufacturing Process Using Polypropyleneby Plastic Injection Molding Method	Mustafa Timur and Halil Kılıç	Turkey	Submission 143
Erzincan Ve Civarındaki Güncel Deprem Etkinliği İçin Gutenberg-Richter b-Değeri Analizi	Fahriye Akar	Turkey	Submission 144
Effect of glass fiber rate on the mechanical and physical properties of Novalac/Gr/Glass fiber hybrid composites	Mücahit Kocaman, Hamdullah Çuvalci and Onur GÜler	Turkey	Submission 145
Effect of graphite particles on the mechanical and physical properties of Novalac/Gr/Glass fiber hybrid composites	Mücahit Kocaman and Hamdullah Çuvalci	Turkey	Submission 146
CLINICAL INFECTIONS OF RESISTANCE SALMONELLA. SP STRAINS ISOLATED FROM FECAL CULTURES AT THE UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL CENTRE OF CONSTANTINE	Rihane Riyane, Hecini-Hannachi Abla and Bentchouala Chafia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 147
Near-Field Communication Wallet	Faruk Ozkan and Omer Aydin	Turkey	Submission 148
Application of Sentiment Analysis for Identifying Trends of the 2021 Moroccan General Election	Ahmed Oussous, Zakaria Boulouard and Fatima Zahra Benjelloun	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 149
Comparison of the Rules of Classification Societies (IACS Members) in the Area of Submersible Maneuvering	Oğuzhan Kirikbaş, Şakir Bal and Mehmet Ali Baykal	Turkey	Submission 150
THE MOBIUS CURVATURE OF BEZIER CURVES	Filiz Ertem Kaya	Turkey	Submission 151
Bibliometric Analysis of the Literature on Marine Mucilage	Taha Talip Türkistanlı, Coşkan Sevgili and Ömer Arslan	Turkey	Submission 152

Session 1.14		1 NOV 2021 17:00-18:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
A DFT study of the optoelectronic properties of Cu-doped CeO ₂ compound	Aicha Bouhlala	Algeria	Submission 154
CCD optimized adsorptive removal of rifampicin using activated carbon alimentary factory waste	Hiba Kais, Nacera Yeddou, Zohra Bensaadi and Amel Hamadi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 155
Cost Savings on Micro grid Operations using Grey Wolf Optimization Algorithm	Gnanaprakash M and Mangaiyarkarasi S.P	India, India	Submission 157
Cellulose based hybrid separators for high performance Li-ion batteries	Meltem Yanılmaz	Turkey	Submission 159
Yüz İfadesini Algılayarak Kullanıcının Ruh Haline Göre İçerik Öneren Mobil Uygulama	İsmail Gündüz and Özgün Yılmaz	Turkey	Submission 160
Mastercam 2022 Programında Takımyolları Oluşturma ve Örnek Uygulama	Mustafa Timur and Halil Kılıç	Turkey	Submission 163
Sürtünme Karıştırma İşleminin Eklemeli İmalat Yöntemi ile Üretilen AlSi10Mg Alaşımının Tribolojik Özelliklerine Etkisi	Hüccet Kahramanzade, Yaşar Sert and Tevfik Küçükömeroğlu	Turkey	Submission 164
Analysis of Output Responses of The Wien Bridge Oscillator Circuit with BJT with Memristor with Different Window Functions	İshak Parlar, M. Nuri Almali and A. Can Çabuker	Turkey	Submission 165
Cost Analysis of Industrial Wastewater Treatment Plants	Nesli AYDINI, Elçin GÜNEŞİ, Gül KAYKIOĞLU1, Abdülkadir MUTLU1, Fatih KAMAOĞLU1	Turkey	Submission 166
Study of the effect of pH on the photoreduction of hexavalent chromium under visible light.	Benalioua Bahia, Benyamina Imane, Mansour Meriem, Mensri Kada and Bentouami Abdelhadi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 167

Session 1.15		1 NOV 2021 18:00-19:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
A Note On Bipartite Graphs with Domination Number 2 and 3	Havva Kırgız and Ayse Dilek Maden	Turkey	Submission 168
Application Areas of Geothermal Waters and Environmental Problems	Saadet Acar and Hasan KÖseoğlu	Turkey	Submission 169
A Novel Method of Analyzing a Reaction Using the Data from Particle and Gamma-ray Detectors	Ilker Can Çelik	Turkey	Submission 170
Effect of Manganese Addition on Crystallographic Features of Bi _{2.1} Sr _{2.0} Ca _{1.1} Cu _{2.0} O _y	Yusuf Zalaoğlu, Asaf Tolga Ulgen and Gurcan Yildirim	Turkey	Submission 172
Role of Manganese Addition on Thermodynamically Activated Super-Electrons in Homogeneous Superconducting Clusters of Bi-2212 Compound	Yusuf Zalaoğlu, Asaf Tolga Ulgen and Gurcan Yildirim	Turkey	Submission 173
Investigation of the Effect of Temperature and Foaming Time on AA2024 Based Metal Foam Production	Sedat Alperen Tunc, Aykut Canakci, Abdullah Hasan Karabacak and Serdar Özkaya	Turkey	Submission 174
Production and Characterization of AA2024 Based Foam Layered Functionaly Graded Composites	Sedat Alperen Tunc, Aykut Canakci and Abdullah Hasan Karabacak	Turkey	Submission 175
Estimating Mechanical Behavior of Scaffolds with Graded Porosity by Finite Element Analysis	Meltem Eryildiz	Turkey	Submission 176
Fonksiyonel Gıda Bileşenlerinin Tespit Edilmesinde Enstrümental Analiz Tekniklerinin Önemi	Pınar Ankaralığıl ve Buket Aydeniz-Güneşer	Turkey	Mail Submission-13
Machining of Metal Matrix Hybrid Nanocomposites with WEDM method	Abdullah Hasan Karabacak, Aykut Canakci, Sedat Alperen Tunc and Serdar Ozkaya	Turkey	Submission 177

Session 1.16		1 NOV 2021 18:00-19:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
The Effect of The Amount of Reinforcement on The Machining of Al ₂ O ₃ -B ₄ C/SiC Hybrid Nanocomposites by AWJ Method	Abdullah Hasan Karabacak, Aykut Canakci and Sedat Alperen Tunc	Turkey	Submission 178
Presentation of Computer Hardware with Virtual Reality	Hanife Boydak, Fatma Nur Canođlu, Fatih Basciftci and Ayşe Kayhan	Turkey	Submission 187
Existence of Periodic and Anti Periodic Solutions in Fractional Order Heat Equations	Münevver Tuz	Turkey	Submission 188
Örgütsel Adalet Algısı ve Mobbingin İş Tatmini ve İşten Ayrılma Niyetine Etkisinin İncelenmesi / Investigation of the Perception of Organizational Justice and the Effect of Mobbing on Job Satisfaction and Intention to Leave of Employment	Muhammet Kahrıman, Selen Avcı and Zerrin Aladađ	Turkey	Submission 189
A numerical investigation of the effect of fiber orientation on the natural frequency of hybrid composite laminate.	Engin Erbayrak	Turkey	Submission 190
Effect of mechanical properties on carbon nanotubes, nanoclays reinforced epoxy carbon fabric composite pipes	Bülent Karaođlu, Hüseyin Arıkan, Mehmet Kayrııcı	Turkey	Submission 191
İn vitro Koşullarda Rejenere Edilen Inula helenium L. Bitkisi ve Kallus Hücre Serilerinde Stresörlerin Biyoaktif Madde Miktarı Üzerine Etkileri	Gökhan Akçura and Musa Türker	Turkey	Submission 193
Enhanced photocatalytic degradation of wastewater using heterogeneous photocatalyst under solar light irradiation	Chagour Nihad, Zouaoui Emna and Chelaghmia Mohamed Lyamine	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 194
SQL Injection Cyber-Attack Scenario and Security Measures in Windows-Based Applications	İsa Avcı, Murat Koca, Merve Atasoy	Turkey	Submission 199
The Usage of ROOT in Analyzing Gamma-rays with Covell and Total Peak Area Methods	Ilker Can Celik	Turkey	Submission 200

Session 1.17		1 NOV 2021 19:00-20:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
INDUSTRY 4.0 PERCEPTION REGARDING TO NEW DEVELOPMENTS AND NEW TRENDS OF INDUSTRIES	Ayşenur Erdil	Turkey	Submission 203
Görme engelli bireyler için derin öğrenme tabanlı nesne tanıma modeli	İsa Avcı and Mehmet Yıldırım	Turkey	Submission 206
Development of Embedded System-Based Lens-less Microscopy System and Testing on Tissue Samples	Muhammed Ali Pala and Mustafa Zahid Yıldız	Turkey	Submission 209
Mermi Hareketinin Modellenmesinde Kullanılan Noble-Abel ve İdeal Gaz Denklemlerinin Akış Alanına Etkisinin Nümerik İncelenmesi	Seyda Ozbektas and Bilal Sungur	Turkey	Submission 210
Isı Transferiyle Çalışan Anemometre Sistemleri	Burak Türüdü	Turkey	Submission 211
Plantar Basınç dağılımı sinyalleri kullanılarak erken MS'lilerde Ataksinin Hybrt CNN modelleri ile belirlenmesi	Aslı Sesli, Seda Arslan Tuncer and Furkan Bilek	Turkey	Submission 212
AKILLI KALİTE KONTROL KAMERALARI VE KARŞILAŞTIRILMASI	Emre Demirkiran	Turkey	Submission 213
Examination of Daily Task Constraint in Technician Routing and Scheduling Problem	Engin Pekel	Turkey	Submission 214
Study of isotherms and mechanism of adsorption of a textile dye by thermally treated dolomite	Boucif Fatima, Bessaha Fatiha, Ziane Samira, Mahrez Nouria and Khelifa Amine	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 217
Effects of bacterial cell concentration on deposition of cells in porous media	Kağan Eryürük	Turkey	Submission 219

Session 1.18		1 NOV 2021 19:00-20:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Removal of azo dye by intercalated halloysite	Nouria Mahrez, Fatiha Bessaha, Gania Bessaha, Fatima Boucif, Samira Ziane and Amine Khelifa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 220
Taş Kolonlarla İyileştirilen Zeminlerin Deprem Etkisinde Taşıma Gücü Analizi: 2020 İzmir Depremi Örneği	Ferhat Şahinkaya and Gökhan Demir	Turkey	Submission 221
Effects of nanofluids on capillary limit in heat pipes	Maroua Mekcem, Mahieddine Berkani and Muhittin Bilgili	Algeria, Algeria, Turkey	Submission 222
Bazı Allium L. Taksonlarının Gövde Anatomik Özelliklerinin İstatistiksel Olarak Karşılaştırılması	Ali Özdemir and Canan Özdemir	Turkey	Submission 223
Potasyum Bromatın Bakla (Vicia faba L.) Kromozomlarına Etkisinin Matematiksel Değerlendirilmesi	Ali Özdemir and Canan Özdemir	Turkey	Submission 224
Numerical Investigation of Water Sloshing in Square Tank with Multiple Baffles	Ferhat Koca and Mustafa Zabun	Turkey	Submission 226
On *-Continuity and *-Uniform Continuity of Some Non-Newtonian Superposition Operators	Fatmanur Erdoğan and Birsen Sağır	Turkey	Submission 227
Mechanochemical Synthesis of COFs: An Eco-friendly Approach	Kashif Ullah Khan	India	Submission 229
Treatment Techniques for Soil Polluted with Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs)	Mahdia Smara, Razika Khalladi, Nadji Moulai Mostefa and Abdellah Ibrir	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 230
THERAPEUTICAL, IN-VITRO AND STABILITY STUDIES OF HERBAL SUPPLEMENT AND PROBIOTICS DERIVED FROM FRUITS, BERRIES, ROOTS, LEAVES AND MACROFUNGUS..	Debasish Sahoo, Virendra Vaishnav, Tanushree Chatterjee and Navita Gupta	India, India, India, India	Submission 232

Session 2.1		2 NOV 2021 09:00-10:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Phytochemical Study of Different Polarity Extracts and Metabolites Isolated From <i>Moltkia Ciliata</i> Growing in Algeria	Oumelkheir Rahim and Soumaia Chihi	Algeria, Albania	Submission 236
Effect of Artificial Aging and Cooling Rate on Microstructure and Mechanical Properties of AA6082	Mehmet Şahbaz	Turkey	Submission 238
Turkey'deki Sucul Ekosistem Kalitesinin Belirlenmesine Yönelik Gerçekleştirilen Biyotik İndeks Çalışmaları	Buse Özalp and Nesil Ertorun	Turkey	Submission 242
İç Anadolu Bölgesi' ndeki Tarım Alanı Değişimlerinin Modis Uydu Verisi ile İzlenmesi	Dilek Küçük Matci	Turkey	Submission 245
Maden Kompleksine ait Fay Zonlarında (Hasenekevleri-Elazığ) Gözlenen Cu-Zn Cevherleşmesinin Jeolojik ve Mikrotermometrik Özellikleri	Cihan Yalçın, Mustafa Kaya, Muhittin Karaman and Mustafa Kumral	Turkey	Submission 246
Long-term behavior of a rational difference equation	Murat Arı and Ali Gelişken	Turkey	Submission 247
Makine Öğrenimi Kullanarak Alacaklar Muhasebesi için Tahmine Dayalı Modelleme	Yunus Emre Mızrakçı and Mehmet Güray Güler	Turkey	Submission 249
Chitin Film Production, Characterization and Evaluation of Cytotoxicity from <i>Caligula japonica</i> Head	Beyza Fırat and Tugce Karaduman	Turkey	Submission 251
Entomological inventory in citrus orchard in Mazagan (Mostaganem)	Aicha Merzoug, Malika Boualem and Faouzia Haffari	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 252
Environmental Friendly Surface Modification Approach to Develop Thin Film Nanocomposite Membrane with Improved Desalination and Anti-scaling Properties	Ying Siew Khoo, Woei Jye Lau, Yong Yeow Liang, Mustafa Karaman, Mehmet Gursoy and Ahmad Fauzi Ismail	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Turkey, Malaysia	Submission 259

Session 2.2		2 NOV 2021 09:00-10:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Metamaterial Embedded Implantable Antenna for Biomedical Applications	Amaria Saidi, Keltouma Nouri and Turkiya Abbes	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 266
N and P doping effects on structural, electronic, and magnetic properties of SrS	Warda Elaggoune and Athmane Meddour	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 267
First principles study of induced half-metallicity in SrS _{1-x} C _x	Warda Elaggoune and Athmane Meddour	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 268
ANALYSIS OF WORK-STUDY-PRODUCTIVITY PRACTICE FOR CORPORATE RESOURCE PLANNING IN A FURNITURE BUSINESS: CASE STUDY	Seher Karakaş, Sümeyye Uçar, Seda Akbal and Ercan Şenyiğit	Turkey	Submission 269
Theoretical Study of Adsorption of Curcumin on Single Walled Carbon Nanotubes	Lina Linda Bechohra, Roya Majidi, Hamza Azzaz, Nor El Houda Medigue and Safia Kellou-Tairi	Algeria, Iran, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 272
Selective Irrigation System Based On IoT And Machine Learning	Harun Dolcel, Mahmut Durgun and Levent Gökrem	Turkey	Submission 273
In-Cylinder Pressure Analysis and Performance of IC Engine Running on Producer Gas from Downdraft Biomass Gasifier	Andi Mulkan and Irvan Dahlan	Indonesia, Malaysia	Submission 274
Effect of viscosity on heat transfer in nanoparticles	Khandan Roshanaei, Edip Taskesen and Mehmet Ozkaymak	Turkey	Submission 278
Dynamic Optimal ANFIS Parameters Tuning with Particle Swarm Optimization	Mahmut Dirik ^{1*} , Mehmet Gül ²	Turkey	Submission 279
Elastic properties of two polymorphs of silica (SiO ₂) in earth's mantle conditions	Radi Zohir, Tlili Salah and Layadi Khalissa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 282

Session 2.3		2 NOV 2021 10:00-11:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Yenilenebilir Enerji Üretiminde Mikrobiyal Biyoproseslerin Kullanımı	Ülkye Dudu Gül and Gizem Bayazıt	Turkey	Submission 283
The Ruled Surfaces with the Parallel Base Curve	Elif Kurt and Fatma Güler	Turkey	Submission 284
Divriği-Selimoğlu Kömürlü İstifinin Hidrokarbon Türüm Potansiyeli ve Termal Olgunluk Özelliği (Sivas, Turkey)	Nazan Yalcin Erik and Harun Çakir	Turkey	Submission 285
Sivas Havzası Güneyinde Üst Kretase – Paleosen Yaşlı Tecer Formasyonunun Organik Petrografik ve Organofasiyes Özellikleri (Ulaş-Sivas)	Nazan Yalcin Erik and Sümeyye Ceyda Yıldız	Turkey	Submission 286
Benefits of BIM (Building Information Modeling) Adoption in Construction Projects: A Case Study	Ibrahim Karatas and Abdulkadir Budak	Turkey	Submission 287
MICROPLASTIC CHARACTERIZATION IN SOIL SAMPLES IN URBAN AND RURAL AREAS OF ESKISEHIR	Esin Huriye Buğdaycı and Burcu Şimşek Uygun	Turkey	Submission 288
Bulanık Mantık Yöntemleriyle Dayanma Duvarının Stabilite Kontrolü	Yusuf Bozkurt, Esra Aslı Çubukçu, Esra Uray and Vahdettin Demir	Turkey	Submission 290
Parçacık Sürü Optimizasyonu ile Konsol Dayanma Duvarının Turkey Bina Deprem Yönetmeliği-2018' e Göre Optimum Tasarımı	Esra Uray and Serdar Çarbaş	Turkey	Submission 291
BOLETUS EDULIS, AN EDIBLE MUSHROOM WITH NUTRITIONNEL VALUE AND HEALTH BENEFITS	Soulef DIB, Kawter SAADANI, Zohra FORTAS	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 16
Performance Analysis of Steepest Descent-Line Search Condition Combinations in Nonlinear Least Square Fitting of CMM Data	Kadir Kiran	Turkey	Submission 293

Session 2.4		2 NOV 2021 10:00-11:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Screening of potential anti-lipase drug from Juniperus phoenicea extracts: In vitro, ADME-Tox, molecular docking and MD-simulation studies	Talia Serseg, Khedidja Benarous, Menouer Serseg and Mohamed Yousfi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 294
Farklı Dolgu Duvarların Betonarme Bir Yapının Sismik Yük Davranışına Etkisinin İncelenmesi	Hasan Furkan Soydoğan, Sadrettin Sancioğlu and Hüsni Can	Turkey	Submission 296
A deep learning approach for detecting pneumonia in chest X-rays	Muhammet Emin Sahin, Hasan Ulutas and Esra Yuce	Turkey	Submission 298
Rubber-Metal Adhesion Systems	Fevziye Erdem and Şeyda Polat	Turkey	Submission 300
Bikompleks Fonksiyonların Bazı Özellikleri Üzerine	Serpil Halici and Şule Çürük	Turkey	Submission 301
Photocatalytic Activity of TiO2 Loaded by Metallic nanoparticles	Meriem Akkar, Nadia Aïcha Laoufi and Abdelkader Mouheb	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 304
Investigation of the Notable Maneuvers of a Low-speed Air Platform to Get Away from Surface-to-Air Threats	Bülent Özkan	Turkey	Submission 306
Investigation of the Performance Characteristics of the Angle-based Proportional Navigation Guidance Law	Bülent Özkan	Turkey	Submission 307
Performance Analysis of Principal Component Analysis and Long Short-Term Memory Networks Using Hydrometeorological Variables for Forecasting of Daily Stream-Flow Data	Levent Latifoğlu	Turkey	Submission 308
Hirshfeld surface analysis, HOMO-LUMO, MEP and NLO investigation of a new thiazole derivative	Guerroudj Ahlam Roufieda, Boukabcha Nourdine and Chouaih Abdelkader	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 310

Session 2.5		2 NOV 2021 11:00-12:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
İş Tatmini Faktörlerini Belirlemeye Ve Analiz Etmeye Yönelik Olarak Çalışanların Çevrimiçi Değerlendirmelerinin Makine Öğrenmesine Dayalı Analizi	Ali Özdemir, Ayтуğ Onan and Vildan Çınarlı Ergene	Turkey	Submission 312
İş Tatmini Faktörlerini Belirlemeye Ve Analiz Etmeye Yönelik Olarak Çalışanların Çevrimiçi Değerlendirmelerinin Sınıflandırıcı Topluluklarına Dayalı Analizi	Ali Özdemir, Ayтуğ Onan and Vildan Çınarlı Ergene	Turkey	Submission 313
Evaluation and Simulation of Proposed Hybrid PTMC/MD Spectral/Spatial Codes in Two Dimensional Optical CDMA Network	Naoum Abderrahmane, Reguieg Sara and Kandouci Chahinaz	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 314
Numerical Investigation of the Effect of Edge Length of Square Helical Wires on Heat Transfer and Pressure Drop	Taha Tuna Gökusu and Rasim Behçet	Turkey	Submission 316
Kademeli Lif Takviyeli Kompozit Beton Kirişlerin Eğilme Davranışı	Abdullah MÜsevİtođlu, Atilla ÖzÜtok, Serkan Salkim, Ođuzhan Çađlar, Gökalp Kirca, Kadirhan ErtÜrk and Mesut Acar	Turkey	Submission 317
Mineral Characterization of Phu Kra dueng Sandstone in Khon Kaen Province	Sukanlayanee Saengsri and Sarunya Promkotra	Thailand, Thailand	Submission 318
FLOOD RISK ASSESSMENT MODELLING TECHNIQUES – A REVIEW	Talha Ahmed, Ishtiaq Hassan	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 320
Ibuprofenin ileri oksidasyon prosesleri ile gideriminin yaşam döngüsü deđerlendirmesi	Sevde ÜstÜn Odabaşı	Turkey	Submission 321
Number of subsets of the set [n] including no three consecutive odd integers	Barış Arslan and Kemal Uslu	Turkey	Submission 322
Evaluation of User Preferences in Urban Parks "The Case of Kyoto Japan Park and Kalehan-Ecdat Park"	Sertaç Güngör and Mine Çakın	Turkey	Submission 323

Session 2.6		2 NOV 2021 11:00-12:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
STUDY THE EFFECT OF PRESSURE ON THE BULK MODULUS OF ALKALINE-EARTH OXIDE CaO WITH SET VALUES AT PREM PRESSURES UP TO 140 GPa BY CALCULATION	Salah Tlili, Zohir Radi, Mohamed Said Nedjimi and Nassiba Ben Atallah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 324
Remedial Measures to Reduce the Harmful Impacts of Tsunami on Buildings –A Review	Muhammad Abrar and Muhammad Usman Farooqi	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 325
Serbest Form Yüzeye Sahip Parçaların Üretim Nedenli Hata Miktarlarının Robot Kol Yardımlı Lazer Sensör ile Tespiti	Abdulkadir Çebi, Muhammed Turan Aslan and Hasan Demirtaş	Turkey	Submission 326
Determination of Sensitivity of Back Trajectories by Using Reanalysis and GDAS Meterology Archive	Firdevs Doğrusever and Deniz Genç Tokgöz	Turkey	Submission 327
A Comparative Study Between Theoretical and Experimental Flexural Capacities of HPRC Beams	Ahmed Altgani Altaher Ahmed, Muhammed Gümüş and Abdussamet Arslan	Sudan, Turkey	Submission 328
GENETIC ALGORITHM IN THE DESIGNATION OF MAXIMAL SECTION VALUES UNDER HORIZONTAL LOAD IN MULTI-STOREY STRUCTURE FRAMES	Atilla Hasdemir and Abdussamet Arslan	Turkey	Submission 331
Inter-laboratory Pressure Comparison Measurement In Gas Medium at ± 150 hPa Range	Yasin Durgut, Recep Yilmaz and Abdullah Hamarat	Turkey	Submission 333
Interlaboratory Comparisons and Their Roles in Laboratory Accreditation	Yasin Durgut	Turkey	Submission 334
Antioxidant and antibacterial potentials of safflower (Carthamus tinctorius L.) flowers extract	Soumia Hadjadj, Imane Guedda, Rokaya Koull and Aminata Ould El Hadj-Khelil	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 336
Fotogrametrik Nokta bulutunun Görünürlük Analizinde Kullanımı: Gümüşhane Seyir Terası Yer Seçimi	Mehmet Akif Günen	Turkey	Submission 338

Session 2.7		2 NOV 2021 12:00-13:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Photocatalytic performance of thermally and chemically treated algerian dolomite in the photodegradation of pentachlorophenol	Choulia Latifa Halloui, Mounir Khelifa, Ilhem Belarbi, Kheira Marouf-Khelifa1, Amine Khelifa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 339
Assessment of Feature Selection for Liquefaction Prediction Based on Recursive Feature Elimination	Selçuk Demir and Emrehan Kutluğ Şahin	Turkey	Submission 343
Removal of mercuric ion by a synthesized new hybrid material	Kenza Drissi, Mhamed Kaid, Hadjer Azzi and Didier Villemain	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, France	Submission 344
Applying response surface methodology to optimize the treatment of wastewater by coagulation-flocculation	Abaidia Meriem, Debab Abdelkader and Khelladi Malika	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 345
Bazı Bitki Kısımlarındaki Geometrik Yapılar	Ali Özdemir and Canan Özdemir	Turkey	Submission 346
Analysys of a mutimotor solution charge repartition for electric vehicles	Liviu Popescu, Leonard Melcescu, Laurențiu Dumitran and Aurelian Craciunescu	Romania, Romania, Romania, Romania	Submission 347
ADSORPTION OF A PHARMACEUTICAL POLLUTION ON LOOFAH	Rekaia Louisa Lakhdari, Nadia Aïcha Laoufi and Abdelkader Mouheb	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 348
Solid-liquid extraction of inorganic pollutants by magnetic nanoparticles	C. Hanagria, I. Benabla B. Haddou, A. Debbeb	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 18
The Diabetic Nephropathy: Study of Some biochemical and physiological Parameters	Ghania Tiboura and Souad Zeggai	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 349
Biochemical characterization and biological activities of aqueous and ethanolic carbohydrate extracts of cotton seeds	Rahim Oumelkheir, Zatout Rabab, Rahmani Youcef and Khelil Aminata	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 350

Session 2.8		2 NOV 2021 12:00-13:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Towards the use of metal-organic framework MOF-5 for the removal of organic dye from aqueous solution: Recent research review	Irvan Dahlan	Malaysia	Submission 351
Recognizing SAR Images from ISAR Training Data	Enes Yiğit, Sevket Demirci and Umut Özkaya	Turkey	Submission 352
Kalp Hastalıklarının Tahmin Edilmesi Karşılaştırmalı Analiz	Ahmet Hamdi Solmaz, Yasin Tiren and Umut Özkaya	Turkey	Submission 353
Comparison of WIM Systems	Nuri Başar	Turkey	Submission 355
İskilip Çileğinin Bazı Fiziko-Kimyasal Özelliklerinin Değerlendirilmesi	Nihal Güzel and K. Savaş Bahçeci	Turkey	Submission 791
Hydraulic Models for Calculating Head Loss in Water Distribution System: a case study in Konya	Kağan Eryürük	Turkey	Submission 357
PERIMENOPAUSE AND BREAST CANCER: ABOUT AN EPIDEMIOLOGICAL, CLINICAL AND HISTOPATHOLOGICAL STUDY	Souad Zeggai and Ghania Tiboura	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 358
Biosorption of textile dye from aqueous solution : kinetic study	Fatiha Bessaha, Gania Bessaha, Imene Toumi, Fatima Boucif, Nouria Mahrez, Samira Ziane and Amine Khelifa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 359
Non-targeted impact of triazole fungicides on the actinobacteria community of activated sludge	Oumeima Boufercha, Irina Sousa Moreira, Paula Maria Lima Castro and Allaoueddine Boudemagh	Algeria, Algeria, Portugal, Portugal	Submission 362
Reference Evapotranspiration Prediction from Limited Climatic Variables Using Support Vector Machines and Gaussian Processes	Yasser Zouzou and Hatice Çıtakoğlu	Turkey	Submission 363

Session 2.9		2 NOV 2021 13:00-14:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Biodiversity of Fusarium spp. responsible for crown rot and fusarium head blight in Algerian wheat; identification of associated species and assessment of their aggressiveness: First report	Hamza Bouanaka, Ines Bellil and Douadi Khelifi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 365
Investigation of sensitive H ₂ S gas sensors based on SnO ₂ -Fe ₂ O ₃ nanoparticles	Ahmad Ayesh and Belal Salah	Qatar, Qatar	Submission 366
Trafik Sinyalizasyon Sisteminde Akıllı Kavşak Kontrolü	Nihat Pamuk	Turkey	Submission 367
The HPLC screening of flavonoids content in Garden cress edible seeds.	Imene Lhadj, Farid Lahfa, Elhadj Ahmed Koceir, Naima Omari	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 368
Anti-inflammatory potential of flavonoids rich extract of Lepidium Sativum Linn seeds in metabolic stress condition.	Imene Lhadj, Lydiaould Amara, Azzi rachid, Elhadj Ahmed Koceir, Naima Omari	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 369
Solunum Hastalıkları ile İlişkili Semptom Seslerinin Sınıflandırılması	Mesut Melek	Turkey	Submission 370
AdaBoost Ensemble Learning on top of Naive Bayes Learner to Discriminate Fake and Genuine News from Social Media	Mehmet Bozuyula	Turkey	Submission 376
BOX-BEHNKEN RESPONSE SURFACE DESIGN OF ANTIOXIDANTS EXTRACTION FROM ELETTARIA CARDAMOMUM SHELL	Merve Bat Özmatara and Şule DİNÇ Zor	Turkey	Submission 377
Sürekli Uzayda Tesis Yeri Seçimi İçin Matematiksel Model: p-Medyan Problemi	Melike Kübra Ekiz Bozdemir, Selen Avcı and Celal Özkale	Turkey	Submission 378
Fast R-CNN based Cavity Detection by using Ground Penetrating Radar	Umut Özkaya and Enes Yiğit	Turkey	Submission 382

Session 2.10		2 NOV 2021 13:00-14:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
ANN based volume calculation of the off-centered conical pile	Enes Yiğit and Umut Özkaya	Turkey	Submission 383
Forecast of the electric energy demand of Turkey using bat algorithm	Şaban Gülcü	Turkey	Submission 384
Comparison of the Performance of Machine Learning Algorithms on Sentiment Analysis Problem in Turkish Texts	Ayşe Berna Altinel Gırgın	Turkey	Submission 385
Kontrol teorisinde sık kullanılan bazı fonksiyonların kesirli dereceden çeşitli türevlerinin farklı yöntemlere göre hata değerlendirilmesi	Mehmet Korkmaz	Turkey	Submission 386
Classification of Type 2 Diabetes Using Machine Learning Techniques	Ziynet Pamuk and Ceren Kaya	Turkey	Submission 745
Super-Bacteria and Their Potential Dangers in the Marine Environments	Samet Kalkan	Turkey	Submission 388
Uncertainty Reasoning in PpLog	Besik Dundua	Georgia	Submission 389
Free Vibration Analysis of Composite Plate Stiffened by Lattice Structures	Serkan Guler	Turkey	Submission 390
Computing Gauss-Bonnet Theorem of σ -Bezier Curves	Filiz Ertem Kaya	Turkey	Submission 234
HSL Renk Uzayında Görüntü İşleme ve Morfolojik İşlemler Kullanarak Gerçek Zamanlı Nesne Tespiti ve Sınıflandırması	Gökhan Atalı and Doğucan Yağmur	Turkey	Submission 393

Session 2.11		2 NOV 2021 14:00-15:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Production of male offshoots of date palm In the Ziban oases (Biskra region south-eastern Algeria)	Rim Ouamane and Salim Khachai	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 394
Effect of water-type on the rheological properties of drilling fluid	Asma Nour El Houda Sid, Benalia Kouini, Abdelkrim Hazourli, Amira Atamnia and Nihad Chagour	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 395
Electro-magneto-hydrodynamic flow and entropy generation in a micro-channel with temperature-dependent properties	Amit Mondal	India	Submission 396
Kimyasal Mordanların Varlığında Nylon Kumaşların Reaktif Boyarmaddelerle Boyanmasının Araştırılması	Güzin Akyol and Behcet Becerir	Turkey	Submission 397
Performance analysis of diabetic retinopathy using diverse image enhancement techniques	Dimple Nagpal and Surya Narayan Panda	India, India	Submission 398
Ölçülen Yapraklanmaların Genelleştirilmiş Dynnikov Koordinat Sistemi	Alev Meral Dülger	Turkey	Submission 399
Technologies Used in Torque Sensor	Hamza Işık	Turkey	Submission 401
Real-Time Acceleration Estimation of a Slider Crank Mechanism with an Enhanced Adaptive Windowing Technique	Ergin Kılıç	Turkey	Submission 403
Convective Heat Transfer and Entropy Analysis on unsteady MHD radiative boundary layer biviscosity nanofluid flow	Susanta Mandal and Gopal Chandra Shit	India, India	Submission 404
Nonlinear Analysis for Composite Steel-concrete Beam under Repeated Loads	Ikhlas Sheet and Bayar Al-Sulafani	Iraq, Iraq	Submission 405

Session 2.12		2 NOV 2021 14:00-15:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
A Proposed Solution for a Safety Traffic Control System Using IoT (STCS)	Ali Alsarhan, Mousa Tayseer Jafar and Mohammad Al-Fawa'Reh	Jordan, Jordan, Jordan	Submission 406
Improved solubility and anti-fungal activity of itraconazole by fabricating thermo-softening and hydrophilic polymers based solid dispersions	Muhammad Irfan and Nayyer Islam	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 408
Güç Kalitesi Sorunlarının Makine Öğrenmesi Yöntemleriyle Sınıflandırılması	Tuğçe Yeşilyurt, Bahadır Akbal and Umut Özkaya	Turkey	Submission 411
Ecological and agrochemical condition of soils of L'viv region of Ukraine as a basis of their investment attractiveness	Anatoliy Demchyshyn, Zinoviï Pankiv and Andriy Kyrylchuk	Ukraine, Ukraine, Ukraine	Submission 415
Investigation of the Use of Reduced Graphene Oxide and Fumed Silica as Support Materials for Gold Nanoparticles in Sorbitol Fuel Cells	Zeynep Daşdelen and Ali Özcan	Turkey	Submission 420
Evaluation of Clustering Algorithms with User Based and Item Based Collaborative Filtering	Kadriye Marangoz and Mustafa Özgür Cingiz	Turkey	Submission 421
Modeling and Characterization of Composite Materials on Microwave Frequencies	Rabah Delfouf, Nacerdine Bouzit and Ncerdine Bourouba	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 422
The Future Trend Natural Preservatives in the Food System: Essential Oils	Gulden Goksen and Pınar Gümüş	Turkey	Submission 423
Petrographic and Geochemical Characteristics of Late Cretaceous Plutonic Rocks Outcropping Western Pertek (Tunceli): First Findings	Mustafa Eren Rizeli	Turkey	Submission 424
Population Biology of <i>Penaeus kerathurus</i> (Forskål, 1755) in the Sea of Marmara	Mukadder Arslan İhsanoğlu, İsmail Burak Daban, Ali İşmen, Koray Cabbar, Haydar Birol İmre, Eylem İmre and Cahide Çiğdem Yiğın	Turkey	Submission 425

Session 2.13		2 NOV 2021 15:00-16:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Petrographic and Geochemical Characteristics of Plutonic Rocks of Elazığ Magmatic Complex outcropping in Geçityaka district in the Southeast Anatolian Orogenic Belt: First Findings	Abdullah Sar	Turkey	Submission 426
Dairesel Sezgisel Bulanık Çok Kriterli Karar Verme Metodolojisi	Esra Çakır, Mehmet Ali Taş	Turkey	Mail Submission 44
Power Allocation Algorithms for Massive MIMO System	Osman Dikmen and Selman Kulaç	Turkey	Submission 429
Effect of PET Waste Having Different Ratio on Mechanical and Durability Properties of Cement Mortars	Arin Yılmaz	Turkey	Submission 430
Antifungal susceptibility of planktonic and sessile <i>Candida albicans</i> clinical isolates	Assia Meradji, Nabil Mosbah, Tayeb Moulahem and Jesus Guinea	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Spain	Submission 672
A bio-flocculant from a waste product: characterization and application to sludge thickening	Yamina Benmerzouka, Abdellah Dahmane, Sid Ahmed Ziat, Hakim Aguedal and Aouatef Driouch	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 436
Mode-Matching Analysis of the Rigid Coaxial Waveguide with an Internal Impedance Loading	Hülya Öztürk	Turkey	Submission 437
Replacement of Extrusion by Temperature-Controlled Ultrasonication in Emulsome Production	Mehmet Hikmet Üçışık	Turkey	Submission 438
Comparison of the cytotoxic effects of <i>Inula viscosa</i> methanol and water extracts on normal and cancer human lung cell lines	Nalan Tavşanlı and Gökçe Taner	Turkey	Submission 439
Solution of Water Distribution Networks Design with Evolutionary Optimization Techniques	Büşra Seval Doğan and Tahir Sağ	Turkey	Submission 441

Session 2.14		2 NOV 2021 15:00-16:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Petrography and Geochemistry of Quaternary Mafic Alkaline Volcanic Rocks in the Elazig Region (Eastern Anatolia/Turkey)	Mehmet Ali Erturk	Turkey	Submission 442
removal of metal ions by activated carbons obtained from two algae	Medjdoub Aicha, Nemchi Fadela, Delali Halima, Belayachi Hanane, Bourahla Sarra and Belhakem Mostefa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 444
Synthesis of NaX zeolite and their heavy metal adsorption properties	Houria Belhouari, Karima Menad and Ahmed Feddag	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 445
Trends in Misuse of Agricultural Lands in of Erzurum Plain of Eastern Turkey	Müdahir Özgül and Emre Çomaklı	Turkey	Submission 446
viscosity of polymers by capillary rheometer, estimation of the molecular mass effect of the constant k of ubbellhode	Nacera Leila Belkhir, Samira Belbachir, Charef Harrats, Amine Harrane and Mahmoud Belailia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 447
Nesnelerin İnterneti Teknolojisinin Kümes Ortamina Uygulanması ve Etkileri	Yeliz Durgun	Turkey	Submission 448
Virulence Gene Profiling of Salmonella spp. Isolated from Bovine and Ovine Meat in Algiers	Siham Nouichi, Lynda Mezali and Taha Mossadak Hamdi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 449
Edge Computing Assisted Anomaly Detection in IoT Systems	Mert Kışlakçı and Mahmut Durgun	Turkey	Submission 450
Plasmonic Photocurrent Improvement in P3HT:PCBM Organic Solar Cells	Mahmoud Fathy, Shima Sanad, Hany Hashem, Ayat Hassanien, Nasr Gad, Mostafa Shaaban, Ashraf Yahia and Moustafa El-Aasser	Egypt, Egypt, Egypt, Egypt, Egypt, Egypt, Egypt, Egypt,	Submission 451
A Different Numerical Perspective for Prey-predator Problem with Harvesting	Nihal Özdoğan, Mevlüde Yakıt Ongun	Turkey	Mail Submission 19

Session 2.15		2 NOV 2021 16:00-17:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Ferric reducing antioxidant power of Peganum harmala seeds fractions.	Meriem Djarmouni, Mofida Adjadj and Abderrahmane Baghiani	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 452
Polimer-polimer karışabilirliğinin guguk kuşu arama algoritmasına dayalı ağırlıklı bulanık sınıflandırma sistemiyle tahmini	Gözde Güldiken, Mehmet Levent Koç and Dilek Imren Koç	Turkey	Submission 453
The effect of pH on the photo reduction of hexavalent chromium under visible light.	Benalioua Bahia	Algeria	Submission 454
Impact on salinity and hardness of Cheliff dam waters in the wilaya of Mostaganem (Algeria)	Sidahmed Ziat, Amina Benmerzouka, Abdellah Dahmane, Hakim Aguedal and Aouate Baghdad	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 455
Strongly \oplus -Locally Artinian Supplemented Modules	Burcu Nişancı Türkmen	Turkey	Submission 456
DEVELOPMENT OF A STARCH-BASED BIO-MATERIAL REINFORCED BY NATURAL FIBERS	Dahmane Abdellah, Benmerzouka Amina, Aguedal Hakim, Baghdad Aouatef and Ziat Sidahmed	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 458
Atık Taşıma Yolu Olarak Kanalların Uygunluk Analizi (Endonezya'daki Makassar Şehri Örneği)	Muhammad Irfan and Ramdan Pano	Turkey, Indonesia	Submission 459
Two-step synthesis of fatty acid methyl ester from waste oil	Soumia Ferarsa and Nadji Moulai-Mostefa	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 460
Subchronic toxicity of the aqueous extract of Solanum sodamaeum L. leaves on liver and kidney function in the wistar rat	Bouchra Baali, Leila Amrani-Kirane and Kheireddine Ouali	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 461
Son İşlem Algoritmaları İçin Web Tabanlı Yazılım Suii Geliştirilmesi	Erdinç Avaroğlu and Didem Öz	Turkey	Submission 463

Session 2.16		2 NOV 2021 16:00-17:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
A Numerical Study on Determining the Effect of Original Evaporator Design on DX-SAHP System Performance	Rıdvan Yakut1	Turkey	Mail Submission 45
α -amylase Inhibitory and Antioxidant Activity of The Phenolic Compounds of Pistacia atlantica Oil	Amel GUERGAB. Chahrazed HAMIA. Mohamed YOUSFI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 20
Thermal performance of earth-air heat exchanger for reducing cooling and heating energy demand of a buildings in temperate climate	Ismail Arroub, Ahmed Bahlaoui and Soufiane Belhouideg	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 466
Numerical investigation of mixed convection in a rectangular cavity with suction of nanofluid: effect of inclination angle	Ismail Arroub, Ahmed Bahlaoui, Soufiane Belhouideg, Abdelghani Raji and Mohammed Hasnaoui	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 467
Numerical solution of mixed convection heat transfer in a multiple vented cavity with injection of nanofluid	Ismail Arroub, Ahmed Bahlaoui, Soufiane Belhouideg, Abdelghani Raji and Mohammed Hasnaoui	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 468
NiO Nanoparticles Induce Cytotoxicity and Oxidative Damage in Human Lung Cells (A549)	Mohamed Khiari and Zine Kechrid	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 469
DA/DA Alçaltıcı Tip Dönüştürücü Devresinin TS-EN 61000-3-2 Standardına Uyumlu Hale Getirilmesi	Ayşenur Özer and Ersoy Kelebekler	Turkey	Submission 470
Monthly Average Electricity Energy Consumption Forecasting with Artificial Neural Networks	Merve Erkınay Özdemir	Turkey	Submission 471
Free vibration analysis of functionally graded plates resting on Winkler–Pasternak elastic foundations using a new shear deformation theory	Redhwane Ait Atmane, Hassen Ait Atmane and Nouredine Mahmoudi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 774
Phytochemical study and antioxidants activities of lipid extrats of Ficus Carica fruit	Hadjira NAOUI, Mohamed YOUSFI and Mohamed BENALIA	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 23

Session 2.17		2 NOV 2021 17:00-18:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Analysis of the Effects of Triggers Like Personal Information and Daily Activities on Migraine Attack with Machine and Deep Learning Approaches	Caglar Gurkan, Sude Kozalioglu and Merih Palandoken	Turkey	Submission 715
Some Generalizations On Fixed Point Theory	Hatice Aslan Hançer	Turkey	Submission 476
modelling of adsorption of phenol on activated carbons using artificial neural network	Hadjer Barki, Salah Hanini and Latifa Khaouane	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 477
Morphological and Molecular Identification of <i>Inocybe alluvionis</i> (Fungi: Basidiomycota) as a new record for Turkey	Sedat Kesici, Aysenur Kalmer, Ayten Dizkirici Tekpinar and Yusuf Uzun	Turkey	Submission 480
A Solar Charger for Lead-Acid Batteries in an Autonomous PV System	Ersagun Kürşat Yaylaci	Turkey	Submission 481
The paradigm for solving the derivation problem in infinite models	Mehmet Kurucan and Mete Özbaltan	Turkey	Submission 482
study and characterization of soils in the seraidi region north east of algeria	Somia Lakehal Ayat and Ibtissem Samai	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 483
Toplu Taşımada Yatırım Kararlarının Veri Madenciliği Yöntemiyle Desteklenmesi	Nur Erdem and Özlem Uzun Araz	Turkey	Submission 484
Effect of 'Avena sativa' on Zinc, Liver Profile, and Antioxidant Levels in Blood and Tissue, in Streptozotocin-Induced Diabetes in Rats Fed a Zinc Low Diet	Ramzi Triki, Khaoula Boughediri and Zine Kechrid	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 485
Compact Embedding Theorems for The Space of Functions with Wavelet Transform in Amalgam Spaces	Öznur Kulak	Turkey	Submission 487

Session 2.18		2 NOV 2021 17:00-18:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Comparison of Feedforward Perceptron Network with LSTM for Solar Cell Radiation Prediction	Tugba Ozdemir, Babajide Ayinde, William Funke, Jacek Zurada and Ozge Tuzun Ozmen	Turkey, USA, USA, USA	Submission 488
Synthesis of microporous materials	Khadidja Soltane, Ahmed Feddag and Djilali Mekhtria	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 489
TRANSFORMATION OF CELLULOSE INTO CELLULOSE NANOCRISTALLINE (CNCs) BY ACID CATALYSIS OF FIBERS OF COTTON	Mohammed Amin Bezzekhami, Amina Mostefai, Mahmoud Belalia, Amine Harrane and Bendhiba Badredine Berfai	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 491
The K-causal Relation in Spacetime Geometry	Himadri Shekhar Mondal and Dwaipayan Mishra	India, India	Submission 493
Strength and Dilation Behaviour of a Reconstituted Sand-Shell Mixture	Suleiman Khatrush	Turkey	Submission 494
A study on electrochemical behaviors of quinoline-based iridium(III) complexes	Ahmet Battal	Turkey	Submission 495
YAPAY ZEKA TEKNİKLERİ KULLANARAK COVID-19 TESPİTİ	Özgür Kart and Fatih Başçiftçi	Turkey	Submission 496
Production and characterization of pumice reinforced Al6061 matrix functional graded composite materials	Mehmet Topuz, Ertan Köseadağ and Mustafa Yasin Gökaslan	Turkey	Submission 498
Yenilebilir Filmlerin Peynir Teknolojisinde Kullanımı	Merve Özcan and Selda Bulca	Turkey	Submission 501
Dimerisation of ϵ -caprolactone using montmorillonite clay as catalyst	Amina Mostefai, Mohammed Amin Bezzekhami, Amine Harrane and Mahmoud Belalia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 502

Session 2.19		2 NOV 2021 18:00-19:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
TOPSİS Çok Kriterli Karar Verme Yöntemi ile Güneş Enerjisi Sistemlerinde Panel Seçimi	Fulya Aslay	Turkey	Submission 509
SIQRV MODELİ VE NÜMERİK UYGULAMASI	Zafer Öztürk, Sezer Sorgun and Halis Bİlgil	Turkey	Submission 510
Setting Reward Function of Sensor Based DDQN Model	Mehmet Gökçay Kabataş and Sevinç İlhan Omurca	Turkey	Submission 511
Number of Subsets of the Set [n] Including No Three Consecutive Even Integers	Barış Arslan and Kemal Uslu	Turkey	Submission 512
Risk Analysis of a Three-Stage Transshipment Network Under a Deliberate Intervention	Fatih Kasimoğlu, Selami Bayeğ and Durdu Hakan Utku	Turkey	Submission 513
Gıda Ürününün Kızılötesi Işınımlı Kurutucu ile Kurutulmasının Optimizasyon Çalışması	Burak Türkan1*, Akın Burak Etemoğlu 2	Turkey	Mail Submission 24
Effect of Pitch Ratio and Diagonal Length of Pin Fin of Heat Sink on Convective Heat Transfer for Turbulent Flow Condition	Noora Imad Haseeb Algburi 1*, Hayati Kadir Pazarlioglu 2 and Kamil Arslan 3	Turkey	Mail Submission 26
Basma Testinin Yüzey Pürüzlülüğüne Etkisinin Sa ve Ra Değerleri Üzerinden İncelenmesi	Mehmet Şahbaz	Turkey	Submission 514
Değişen Sodyum Nitrat Konsantrasyonları ile Elde Edilen Grafen Oksit Üretimlerinde: Kısım 1, X Ray Difraksiyonu Analizi	Ömer Laçın and Bünyamin Dönmez	Turkey	Submission 515
Değişen Sodyum Nitrat Konsantrasyonları ile Elde Edilen Grafen Oksit Üretimlerinde: Kısım 2, X Işını Fotoelektron Spektroskopisi Analizi	Ömer Laçın and Bünyamin Dönmez	Turkey	Submission 516

Session 2.20		2 NOV 2021 18:00-19:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Değişen Sodyum Nitrat Konsantrasyonları ile Elde Edilen Grafen Oksit Üretimlerinde: Kısım3, Fourier Dönüşümlü Kızılötesi Spektroskopisi Analizi	Ömer Laçın and Bünyamin Dönmez	Turkey	Submission 517
Değişen Sodyum Nitrat Konsantrasyonları ile Elde Edilen Grafen Oksit Üretimlerinde: Kısım 4, Raman Spektroskopisi Analizi	Ömer Laçın and Bünyamin Dönmez	Turkey	Submission 518
Development and Simulation of 39 DOF Vehicle Model	Adem Tunçdamar	Turkey	Submission 520
Numerical Analysis of the Offshore Pile	Engin Gücüyen and Recep Tuğrul Erdem	Turkey	Submission 521
Molecular and morphological identification of wild edible fungus species; <i>Leucoagaricus barssii</i> and <i>Leucoagaricus leucothites</i>	Ayten Dizkırıcı Tekpınar, Aysenur Kalmer and Ismail Acar	Turkey	Submission 526
Variation of C: N ratios in White birch (<i>Betula verrucosa</i> Ehrh.) afforestation area among different plant organs and soil	Emre Çomaklı and Tuğba çomaklı	Turkey	Submission 529
Dielectric analysis of high voltage equipment via 3D partial discharge signal graphics	Tuba Nur Serttaş, Fatih Serttas	Turkey	Submission 530
Akımsız Ni-P-W Kompozit Kaplamalarda PTFE Konsantrasyonunun Sertlik Ve Aşınma Üzerinde Etkisi	Serdar Aslan, Erhan Duru	Turkey	Mail Submission-186
An in-depth exam of IoT, IoT Core Components, IoT Layers, and Attack Types	Muhammed Yildirim, Uğur DemİroĞlu and Bilal Şenol	Turkey	Submission 532
Essential oils as control agents of postharvest <i>Alternaria</i> rots on tomato fruit during storage	Amina Tabet Zatla, Amina Hammoudi and Mohamed El Amine Dib	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 533

Session 2.21		2 NOV 2021 19:00-20:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Experimentally Investigation of Some Facilities Provided by Hybrid UPSs	İbrahim Güneş, Osman Okay and Emre Akarşlan	Turkey	Submission 534
Çift Bantlı RF Enerji Hasadı İçin Toplu Eleman Devre Yapıları	Filiz Sarı	Turkey	Submission 535
Cycloidal Surfaces	Erhan Güler and Ömer Kişi	Turkey	Submission 536
Helicoidal Surfaces Constructed by Lemniscate Curve: Lemniscatoidal Surface	Erhan Güler and Ömer Kişi	Turkey	Submission 537
Morphological and Molecular Identification of a Rare Fungus Species; Hebeloma salicicola, as a First Record for Turkey	Aysenur Kalmer, Ayten Dizkirici Tekpinar and İsmail Acar	Turkey	Submission 538
Speed Gradient Control Algorithm for Optogenetic Modeling	Sergey Borisenok	Turkey	Submission 539
On Asymptotically f- Rough Lacunary Invariant Equivalence of Double Sequences via Ideals	Ömer Kişi and Erhan Güler	Turkey	Submission 540
Rough Lacunary Statistical Convergent Functions via Ideals with regards to the Intuitionistic Fuzzy Normed Spaces	Ömer Kişi and Erhan Güler	Turkey	Submission 541
Çoklu Kaynak Gerektiren Parçalarda Kaynak Sırasının Genetik Algoritma Kullanılarak Belirlenmesi	Onur Yurdakul and Başar Yavuz	Turkey	Submission 542
A Mathematical Model for Flow Shop Scheduling Problem with Blocking Constraint and Sequence-dependent Setup Time	Ahad Furugi	Turkey	Submission 545

Session 2.22		2 NOV 2021 19:00-20:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
İn Vitro Şartlarda Rejenere Edilen Hypericum perforatum L. Bitki Ekstraktlarından Üretilen Nanoparçacıkların Antikanser Etkilerinin Araştırılması	Nuran Çalıklı and Musa Türker	Turkey	Submission 546
Evaluation of the Antioxidant Effects of Postbiotics and Paraprobiotics in Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated from Traditional Fermented Sausages	Betül Aydın, Tuğçe Çiydem, Esra Kaya and Leyla Açık	Turkey	Submission 548
GREY WOLF OPTIMIZER ALGORITHM FOR AGC OF TWO-AREA POWER SYSTEM	Sercan Ozumcan, Ali Ozturk and Cenk Andic	Turkey	Submission 549
Hybrid Convolutional Neural Network Architectures for Skin Cancer Classification	Emine Cengil, Ahmet Çınar and Muhammet Yıldırım	Turkey	Submission 550
Hereditary and Productive of Local Pre-Hausdorff Objects in ConFCO	Osman Çeltik and Ayhan Erciyes	Turkey	Submission 551
Highly potent thiazole-appended "switch off" fluorogenic chemoprobe with capable of detecting Cu (II) in solutions	Duygu Aydın and Huseyin Kucukbasmaci	Turkey	Submission 552
A Numerical Algorithm for Solving Second-order Parabolic Equations with Exponential Nonlinearity	Asuman Zeytinoglu	Turkey	Submission 554
Phenomenology of the pretreatment by gliding arc discharge: experimental and modeling study	Bilal Belmekki, Mouffok Redouane Ghezzar, Fouad Ferhat and Ahmed Addou	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 555
Evaluation of Ensemble Algorithms and Deep learning Transformers in Medical Sentiment Prediction	Akın Özçift and Mehmet Bozuyula	Turkey	Submission 556
Uçak Bakım Teknisyenleri için DEMATEL Yöntemi ile Fiziksel İş Yükü Faktörlerinin Değerlendirilmesi	Yaşar Öztürk, Ebru Yazgan, Elif Kılıç Delice	Turkey	Mail Submission 28

Session 2.23		2 NOV 2021 20:00-21:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Manufacturing low-cost flexible thermoplastic pulsating heat stripes	Oguzhan Der, Volfango Bertola	Turkey, UK	Mail Submission 29
Development of peptide-based imaging agent for use in Cancer Diagnosis	Derya CIN, Hayat Dilan ONSAL, Sevgi GULYUZ1, Cem Bulent USTUNDAG, Sefer BADAY, Güneş ESENDAGLI, Onur ALPTURK, Ozgur YILMAZ	Turkey	Mail Submission 30
Impact of Fe ₃ O ₄ /water on Natural Convection in Square Enclosure	Hayati Kadir Pazarlioglu, Mutlu Tekir	Turkey	Mail Submission 31
Impact of poorly maintained wastewater sewage treatment plants on dessimination of multi-resistant bacteria in the environment	Fatima Zohra Mokeddem	Algeria	Submission 557
Comparison of Some Numerical Approaches for Determination of Dynamic Characteristics in Beam and Plate Elements	Mustafa Tolga Yavuz and Ibrahim Ozkol	Turkey	Submission 558
Development and characterization of a material environmentally friendly made from PEHD loaded with vegetable fibers.	Djihane Slimane Ben Ali, Ferial Krid, Habiba Tabet and Amira Atamnia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 560
Novel Y-shaped dipole Antenna with Stubs for UWB applications	Yamina Bekri and Tewfik Khiat	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 561
Effect of different ultrasonic amplitude treatments on corn starch gels	Gamze Üçok	Turkey	Submission 562
Preliminary phytochemical study of Haloxylon scoparium Pomel., a medicinal plant from Algeria	Mustapha Chelghoum, Walid Khitri and Dalila Smati	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 563
Application of NMR spectroscopy in the structural determination of a saponin from Bupleurum rigidum	Mustapha Chelghoum, Dalila Smati and Marie-Allethe Lacaille-Dubois	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 565

Session 2.24		2 NOV 2021 20:00-21:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Vorticity Distribution on a Surface Mounted Cube at Re=10000	Mehmet Beşkirli and Mehmet Fatih Tefek	Turkey	Submission 567
On Delta-ss-Supplementing Modules	Esra Öztürk Sözen	Turkey	Submission 570
The Effect of Glass Fiber and Water Content on Shear Strength of Clayey Soil	Mehmet Fatih Yazıcı, Ahmetcan Sungur and Sıddıka Nilay Keskin	Turkey	Submission 574
Exploring the candidate genes in the formation of type 2 diabetes-induced pancreatic cancer via bioinformatics analysis	Hamid Ceylan	Turkey	Submission 575
Investigation of Mechanical Properties of Si3N4 Reinforced Composites Produced from Aluminum Waste	Burak Öztop and Mevlüt Gürbüz	Turkey	Submission 576
Experimental Research on the Engineering Properties of Basalt Fiber Reinforced Clayey Soil	Ahmetcan Sungur, Mehmet Fatih Yazıcı and Sıddıka Nilay Keskin	Turkey	Submission 577
Adsorption of chromium(III) on chert	Najah Mahjoubi and Manel Araïssi	Tunisia, Tunisia	Submission 578
Nanocellulose prepared by an enzymatic treatment of isolated cellulose from schinus molle	Abir Razzak and Ramzi Khiari, Younes Moussaoui	Tunisia, Tunisia, France	Submission 579
Effects of black rice milk on growth and survival of Lactobacillus acidophilus	Samin Toupal and Serap Coşansu	Turkey	Submission 580
An off-on fluorescence chemoprobe based on furazan derivative for the sensing of Al ³⁺	Şükriye Nihan Karuk Elmas	Turkey	Submission 581

Session 3.1		3 NOV 2021 10:00-11:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
TEMPO-Mediated Oxidation of cellulose isolated from schinus molle	Abir Razzak and Ramzi Khiari, Mohamed Naceur Belgacem, Younes Moussaoui	Tunisia, Tunisia, France, France	Submission 582
Adsorption of cationic dye methyle bleu using chert	Najah Mahjoubi and Manel Araïssi, Elimame Elaloui,	Tunisia, Tunisia, Tunisia	Submission 583
Earthquake Behaviors of Highway Bridges with Elastomeric Bearings for Different Pier Column Heights	Yersayn Bexultan and Ali İhsan Karakaş	Turkey	Submission 584
Antibacterial activity of three Algerian endemic plants against Pseudomonas aeruginosa	Benaïssa Asma, Khadir Abdelmounaim, Bendahou Mourad and Latti Nawel	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 585
Determination of Bacterial Isolates from Pesticide Contaminated Agricultural Area	Merve Yavas and Tugba Ozaktas	Turkey	Submission 586
HYPERBOLIC VALUED DISLOCATED METRIC SPACES	Nilay Değirmen	Turkey	Submission 587
TEMPO-Mediated Oxidation of cellulose isolated from schinus molle	Abir Razzak and Ramzi Khiari, Mohamed Naceur Belgacem, Younes Moussaoui	Tunisia, Tunisia, France, France	Submission 582
Design and Evaluation of the PV Simulator with Modified P&O Algorithm	Ersagun Kürşat Yaylaci, Mohammad Al Msalma and Novruz Mammadli	Turkey	Submission 591
Comparative study of the stabilization/solidification process of oil cuttings using hydraulic and organic binders.	Lounas Oualid and Malek Ammar	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 592
Effect of Dunaliella salina on enhancing viability of probiotic and the nutritional value	Zina Alajil Alslibi, Abuzer Çeleklî and Hüseyin Bozkurt	Turkey	Submission 593

Session 3.2		3 NOV 2021 10:00-11:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
EFFECT OF NANOPARTICLE SHAPE AND VOLUME FRACTION ON NANOFUID FLOW IN SERPENTINE MICROTUBE	Fethi Murat Altunay and Kamil Arslan	Turkey	Submission 594
Venomous and Non-Venomous Snakes of Morocco	Abderrafea Elbahi and Jamila Hermas	Morrocco, Morrocco	Submission 595
Thermal effect on reliability and efficiency of 5nm DG-FinFET Transistors	Nassima Bourahla and Fatima Zohra Boudjenane	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 596
Species-Richness and Endemism of Souss-Massa National Park Reptiles	Abderrafea Elbahi, Colin Lawton, Jamila Hermas and Michel Dugon	Morrocco, Morrocco, Ireland, Ireland	Submission 597
Optimization of extraction of phenolic compounds from potato by-products using response surface methodology	Fatiha Brahmi, Nadjet Abaci, Salima Saoudi, Khodir Madani and Lila Boulekbache-Makhlouf	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 598
THE PRODUCTION OF UNSATURATED POLYESTER RESIN BASED COMPOSITE FILLED WITH MARBLE POWDER WASTE AS MINERAL CHARGE	Rahima Baghloul, Laidi Babouri and Ouided Dehas	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 599
New Trends in Determining Soil Properties	Asena Karshoğlu, Ahmet Ali Mert and Mehmet İnanç Onur	Turkey	Submission 600
Keçi Sütünden Mikrobiyal Transglutaminaz (mTGaz) Enziminin İki Farklı Starter Kültürü ile Yanıt Yüzey Yöntemiyle Yoğurt Üretiminde Kullanılması Ürün Optimizasyonu ve Bu Yoğurtların Bazı Özelliklerinin Saptanması	Selda Bulca, Burcu Güvenç, Mehmet Çelebi and Mürüvvet Abbak	Turkey	Submission 601
A Printed Antenna Design with Defected Ground Structure for Multiband Applications	Maie Gaber, Faten Fouad, Ashraf Yahia, Mostafa El-Aasser and Nasr Gad	Egypt, Egypt, Egypt, Egypt, Egypt	Submission 602
A multiple-target chemoprobe: "naked-eye" colorimetric recognition of Fe ³⁺ and off-on fluorogenic detection for Hg ²⁺	Tahir Savran, Sukriye Nihan Karuk Elmas, Duygu Aydın, Sumeyye Arslan, Fatma Nur Arslan and Ibrahim Yilmaz	Turkey	Submission 603

Session 3.3		3 NOV 2021 11:00-12:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Prediction of the global solar fluxes using cloud cover and meteorological parameters in Morocco	Halima Yakoubi, Youness El Mghouchi and Abdeljabar Khellouki	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 604
Esnek Bir Kirişin SimMechanics ve Sonlu Eleman Modellerinin Karşılaştırılması	Mehmet Uyar	Turkey	Submission 605
Deneysel olarak ölçülen farklı sürüş davranışlarının K en yakın komşuluklar yöntemleriyle sınıflandırılması	Tuba Nur Serttaş and Fatih Serttaş	Turkey	Submission 606
Using Machine Learning Methods for Credit Card Fraud Detection	Ömer Faruk Akmeşe	Turkey	Submission 607
YAPAY ZEKA 'NIN KÜLTÜR VE SANATLA OLAN İLİŞKİSİ	Yusuf Uzun and Beyzanur Akkuzu, Mehmet Kayırcı	Turkey	Submission 608
Güneş Enerjisi Üretimine Yapay Zeka ile Tahminlenmesi: İzmir Bakırçay Üniversitesi Örneği	Özgün Uz and Özge Tüzün Özmen	Turkey	Submission 613
Flame retardancy properties of Polyamide 11/Palygorskite nanocomposites	Baya Benobeidallah, Mustapha Kaci, José-Marie Lopez-Cuesta and Aida Benhamida	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 615
Eklmeli İmalat Prosesi için 3 Boyutlu Yazıcıların Özelliklerinin İncelenmesi- Investigation of the Properties of 3D Printers for Additive Manufacturing Processes	Fatma Nazli Özsolak and Bülent Kaya	Turkey	Submission 616
Physico-chemical characterization of sludge from the paper industry	Meriem Merah, Samira Maane and Chahra Boudoukha	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 618
Retrospective study of COPD associated with tobacco smoking and biomass smoke	Nada Slama, Karima Bahria, Amira Bouguedra and Karine Benachour	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 621

Session 3.4		3 NOV 2021 11:00-12:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Üzerinde Aykırı Devirli Kodlar İçin Bazı Sonuçlar	basri çalışkan	Turkey	Submission 490
KANAT GÖVDE TİPİNDEKİ BİR İNSANSIZ HAVA ARACININ YAPISAL TASARIMI VE ANALİZİ	Aybuke Gökçen Yılmaz İlaslan, ilyas kandemir	Turkey	Mail Submission 36
Identification of COVID-19 from Cough Sounds Using Non-Linear Analysis and Machine Learning	Fatma Zehra SOLAK	Turkey	Mail Submission 37
Evaluation of Antioxidant and Anti-inflammatory Activities of Paronychia argentea Medicinal Plant Extracts	Moufida ADJADJ, Meriem DJARMOUNI, Fatima ZERARGUI, Karima SAFFIDINE and Abderrahmane BAGHIANI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 38
Kinetic study of Teflon Blue dye biosorption on Typha as biosorbent: Modeling	El Khamssa. Guechi, Soulef. Benabdesselam, Oualid. Hamdaoui	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 40
Bulanık FUCOM Metodu ile Tedarikçi Değerlendirme Kriterlerinin Ağırlıklarının Belirlenmesi	Merve Ceren TAŞKENT, Elif Kılıç Delice	Turkey	Mail Submission 41
HTEA Tabanlı KEMIRA-M Yöntem ile Sağlık Sektöründe Risk Değerlendirme	Nuray ARSLAN1, Elif KILIÇ DELİCE 2*	Turkey	Mail Submission 42
Quantitative risk assessment of LNG release in storage and loading unit - Case study of Skikda-Algeria LNG terminal	Sarra Chebli, Chérif Tolba and Youcef Zennir	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 625
Treatment of an anthraquinonic dye by gliding arc: Modeling and simulation study	Ramzi Abdelmutaleb Debba, Bilal Belmekki and Mouffok Redouane Ghezzar	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 626
A New Copper(II) Complex: Active Catalyst For Homogeneous Olefin Epoxidation.	Souad Dekar, Moufida Merzougui and Kamel Ouari	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 627

Session 3.5		3 NOV 2021 12:00-13:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Influence of geometric parameters on the average outlet velocity of the Bladeless Fan	Doğukan Akgöl	Turkey	Submission 292
Investigation of the effects of <i>Lavandula officinalis</i> Mill. and <i>Melissa officinalis</i> L. species belonging to Lamiaceae family on COX anti-inflammatory pathway enzyme	Kübra Şener, Murat Ekici, Ekrem Murat Gönülalan and Ebru Bodur	Turkey	Submission 632
Unsteady Bioconvective Squeezing Flow with Higher Order Chemical Reaction and Second Order Slip Effects	Raju Bag, Nilankush Acharya and Prabir Kumar Kundu	India, India, India, India	Submission 634
Effect of rotational speed on temperature distribution in friction stir welding for dissimilar Al alloy sheets	Yasin Sarıkavak	Turkey	Submission 636
Global Optimizasyon Problemleri için Kaotik Bonobo Algoritması	Sumeyye Bazna and Sinem Akyol	Turkey	Submission 637
Synthesis and Characterization of Tetrazoloquinoline-BODIPY dyes	Yavuz Derin and Barış Seçkin Arslan	Turkey	Submission 641
Sac Malzeme Üretiminde Hata Türleri ve Etkileri Analizi	Batuhan Özakın	Turkey	Submission 642
Optimization of extraction conditions of phenolic compounds from <i>Erica multiflora</i> L. by the experimental design	Naima Boucheffa-Guendouze, Sonia Madouni, Lynda Mekhazni, Baya Iamaren, Khodir Madani and Lila Boulekbache	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 644
Content of bioactive compounds and antioxidant activity of mashed potato extract, and its incorporation into yogurt	Naima Boucheffa-Guendouze, Katia Zakane, Laldja Tahar, Sana Kerrour, Leila Benazzouz, Khodir Madani and Lila Boulekbache-Makhlouf	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 646
Identifying Human Activity Using Machine Learning Algorithms with Gyroscope and Accelerometer Data	Cem Özkaya and Mustafa Yasin Esas	Turkey	Submission 648

Session 3.6		3 NOV 2021 12:00-13:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Study of the Pathogenicity of Fusarium spp. Isolates on the Basal Part of Some Varieties of Durum Wheat (<i>Triticum durum</i>) in Algeria	Imene Belabed, Nouredine Rouag, Omar Bencheikh and Hanene Abed	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 650
From Eco-friendly sonochemical synthesis of a new unsymmetrical oxovanadium complex to structural and electrochemical properties	Moufida Merzougui, Souad Dekar and Kamel Ouari	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 651
Some Notions on Interval-Valued Neutrosophic Sets	Yıldırım Çelik	Turkey	Submission 654
Determination of Proline Contents and Physicochemical Properties of Mono/polyfloral and Honeydew Honeys Produced in Turkey for the Assessment of Adulteration	Merve Özbay, Fatma Nur Arslan and Gazi Görür	Turkey	Submission 655
Detection of Heart Diseases Using Machine Learnings	Mustafa Coşar and Emre Deniz	Turkey	Submission 658
Occurrence and characteristics of staphylococci and enterococci in retail fish used for human consumption in Turkey	Meryem Burcu Külahcı and Neslihan Gündoğan	Turkey	Submission 659
Grafen Oksit Katkılı Kitosan/Hidroksipropil Metilselüloz Biyanokompozit Film Sentezi ve Anti-Kanser İlacı 5-Fluorourasil'in Kontrollü Salımında Kullanımı	Mürüt Akal, Muhammed Emre Demirdere and Derya Ünlü	Turkey	Submission 773
Derin Öğrenme Mimarilerini Kullanarak Katarakt Tespiti	Muhammed Fatih AĞalday and Ahmet Çinar	Turkey	Submission 661
Stability Analysis of an Epidemic Model of Fractional Order with a General Nonlinear Incidence and a Treatment Function	Esra Karaoğlu	Turkey	Submission 664
Effect of Richardson number and Temperature-Dependent viscosity on mixed convection Combined with thermal radiation in lid-driven square cavity filled with a shear-thinning fluid	Ilham Erritali, Mourad Kaddiri, Hamza Daghbab and Ismail Arroub	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 665

Session 3.7		3 NOV 2021 13:00-14:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Meeting Irrigation Demand of Agricultural Land by the Off-Grid Solar-Wind Hybrid Renewable Energy System with Battery Storage	Ahmet Erhan Akan and Aytac Perihan Akan	Turkey	Submission 666
FUZZY LOGIC CONTROL AUTOMATION FOR TRAFFIC SIGNALIZATION SYSTEM	Ecem Acar and Sevilay Kirci Serenbay	Turkey	Submission 667
FUNCTIONAL CHARACTERIZATION OF HASLEA OSTREARIA TERPENOID SYNTHASE THROUGH SYNTHETIC BIOLOGY APPROACHE IN THE MODEL DIATOM SPECIES PHAEODACTYLUM TRICORNUTUM	Amel Khitem Benali, Frederic Verret, Faouzia Zemani-Fodil, Mohamed Bey Baba Hamed and Ahlem Messal	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Greece	Submission 669
Biofilm forming ability by clinical isolates of Candida species : Comparison of biomass production and metabolic activity	Assia Meradji, Nabil Mosbah, Tayeb Moulahem and Jesus Guinea	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Spain	Submission 670
Effect of particle size of the raw Algerian bentonite on rheological properties of the ecological drilling mud	Selma Medjahed, Abdelbaki Benmounah and Abderazak Gueciouer	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 671
Yöneylem Araştırması Alanında Yapılan Çalışmaların Bibliyometrik Analizi	Özlem Çomaklı Sökmen and Mustafa Yılmaz	Turkey	Submission 673
Synthesis and characterization of Fe ₃ O ₄ doped polymeric nanoparticles as a novel affinity adsorbent	Recep Üzek	Turkey	Submission 678
Parkinson Hastalarının Dikkat Fonksiyonlarının Cinsiyet Açısından Değerlendirilmesi: Bir fMRG Çalışması	Nur Yılmaz and Güzin Özmen	Turkey	Submission 679
Efficient trajectory generation for any polygonal pocket boundary with CPO tool paths	Elhachemi Bahloul and Cherif Rebiai	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 680
Atık Polistiren Matrisli Aerojel Takviyeli Kompozitlerin Üretimi ve Karakterizasyonu	Amin Fiyouj and Mevlüt Gürbüz	Turkey	Submission 681

Session 3.8		3 NOV 2021 13:00-14:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
A Comparative Study on Gas Alarm Detection System	Muhammad Baballe Ahmad, Mukhtar Ibrahim Bello, Adamu Alkali Umar, Isa Ibrahim and Aliyu Lawan Musa	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 683
A Study on the Impact and Challenges of Temperature Detection System	Muhammad Baballe Ahmad, Mukhtar Ibrahim Bello, Auwal Ishaq Balarabe, Usman Yusuf Magashi and Fatihu Muhammad	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 685
Immunomodulatory activity and reducing power of Algerian endemic Centaurea SP n-butanol extract.	Hichem Mezdour, Ahmed Menad and Souad Amedah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 686
Bir Üretim İşletmesinde Simülasyon Yöntemi ile Darboğaz Analizi ve Sistem İyileştirmesi	Ege Cihangir, Fatma Demircan Keskin, Ural Gökay Çiçekli and Gökhan Yakan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 687
A review on the Impact of Solar Power Energy	Muhammad Baballe Ahmad	Nigeria	Submission 688
A Study on the Components used in Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) System and its Challenges	Muhammad Baballe Ahmad	Nigeria	Submission 689
EQUIVALENCES BETWEEN THE CATEGORIES	Ummahan Ege Arslan and Elis Soylu Yılmaz	Turkey	Submission 690
Hava-Jetli Tekstüre Politrimetilen Tereftalat (PTT) İpliklerin Üretimi ve Karakterizasyonu	Hakan Gedikli and Serpil Koral Koç	Turkey	Submission 691
Tasarım Süreçlerinde Otomasyon Sistemlerinin Optimizasyonu ve Etkilerinin İncelenmesi	Burak GÜL and Ersin Toptaş	Turkey	Submission 692
Mobil Kontrol- Görüntü Aktarımı ve Lazer Savunma Gücüne Sahip Tank Robot Tasarımı	Burak Kapusiz	Turkey	Submission 693

Session 3.9		3 NOV 2021 14:00-15:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
In-vitro characterization of potentially probiotic Apilactobacillus strain isolated from Algerian fresh honey	Meriem Meradji, Nadia Bachtarzi, Karima Kharroub and Diego Mora	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Italy	Submission 694
Determination of Parameters Affecting Critical Buckling Loads of Curved Laminated Composite Plates	Cenk Yanen, Murat Can Tanış and Murat Yavuz Solmaz	Turkey	Submission 699
Dıştan Dişli Pompalarda Farklı Hidrolik Yağ Sıcaklıklarının Pompa Performansı Üzerindeki Etkileri	Üsame Ali Usca and Mahir Uzun	Turkey	Submission 700
Mikro Denetleyici Sistemler ile Türk İşaret Dili Kelime Çevirici	Fatih GÖKÇe and Hakan KekÜl	Turkey	Submission 701
A Conceptual Design of LoRa based Weather Monitoring System for Smart Farm Management	Hakkı Soy and Yusuf Dilay	Turkey	Submission 702
Membrane based Energy Recovery Ventilator: Fundamentals and Regression Analysis	Muhammad Asif, Muhammad Sultan, Zahid M. Khan and Hasan Köten	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Turkey	Submission 703
Assessment of Atmospheric Water Harvesting Potential using Direct Cooling Method for Pakistan and Turkey	Muhammad Bilal, Muhammad Sultan, Muhammad Ali Imran and Hasan Köten	Pakistan, Pakistan, China, Turkey	Submission 704
On Harmonic Univalent Functions Involving (p,q)-Poisson Distribution Series	Hasan Bayram and Sibel Yalçın	Turkey	Submission 705
Investigating Air-Conditioning Options for the Storage of Hides and Skins in Pakistan	Hasham Ul Haq, Hadeed Ashraf, Muhammad Sultan, Zahid M. Khan and Muhammad Ali Imran	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, China	Submission 706
On the Desiccant and Evaporative Cooling Options for Livestock Air-Conditioning	Hafiz M.U. Raza and Muhammad Sultan	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 707

Session 3.10		3 NOV 2021 14:00-15:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
A theoretical study of the synthesized (Z)-3-N-(ethyl)-2-N'-((3-methoxyphenyl)imino)thiazolidine-4-one and its NLO properties ,molecular docking analysis	Boudjenane Fatima Zohra, Chouaih Abdelkader, Boukabcha Nourdine, Bourahla Nassima and Bouldiab Yasmine	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 708
The impact of local wastewater sewage sludge on the mechanical properties of mortar	Fouzia Benoudjit and Messaoud Hachemi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 710
Determination of the Genetic Diversity of Salmonella spp. Strains Isolated from Bovine and Ovine Samples in Algiers, Algeria	Siham Nouichi, Lynda Mezali, Taha Mossadak Hamdi, Christian Vinueza-Burgos and Lieven De Zutter De Zutter	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Ecuador, Belgium	Submission 712
Preparation and microstructural study of undoped nickel oxide thin films	Amel Haichour and Nasr-Eddine Hamdadou	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 713
The effect of orientation and pressure on the subcooled flow boiling performances in minichannel	Amal Igaadi, Rachid El Amraoui and Hicham El Mghari	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 716
Numerical study of free convection for fluids with temperature-dependent viscosity in a partially heated square enclosure from below	Hamza Daghab, Mourad Kaddiri, Said Raghay, Ismail Arroub, Ilham Erritali and Redouane Nouri	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 717
Injection of the quantities of a photovoltaic system into the electricity network (modeling and simulation)	Kihal Hafidha	Algeria	Submission 718
Gıda Örneklerinden İzole Edilen Enterococcus Türlerinin Çeşitli Virülans Özellikleri Biyofilm Oluşumu ve Antibiyotik Dirençliliklerinin Belirlenmesi	Tuğçe Gürkan, Meryem Burcu KÜlahci and Sumru Çitak	Turkey	Submission 720
Natural convection of non-Newtonian fluids in power law in a square cavity with a crossed temperature gradient	Redouane Nouri, Hamza Daghab, Mourad Kaddiri and Youssef Tizakast	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 723
Nosocomial infections and antibiotic sensitivity of Enterobacter sp isolated from the hospital of Medea (Algeria)	Amina Zergoug	Algeria	Submission 724

Session 3.11		3 NOV 2021 15:00-16:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Recent Development of Polymer Based Membranes in Microbial Fuel Cells	Sema Tuğçe Baykara	Turkey	Submission 802
Immobilization of Porcine Pancreatic Lipase Enzyme in a Membrane Incorporating BSA and Glutaraldehyde for the Detection of Propyl Paraben.	Snani Leila, Zougar Saida and Benamia Fatiha	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 726
Atıksularda Koronavirüslerin Akıbetinin Araştırılması ve Erken Uyarı Sistemi Yaklaşımı Üzerine Bir Derleme	Sevde üstün Odabaşı	Turkey	Submission 736
Bandwidth Enhancement of Microstrip Patch Antenna using Quad L-shape slot and DGS for X-band Applications	Auwalu Aminu Abubakar, Sulaiman Aliyu Babale, Zainab Yunusa and Lawal Muhammad Bello	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 739
Fabrication and Characterization of Mullite Reinforced MgO Added ZrO ₂ Ceramics	Mehmet Akif Hafizoğlu, Tahsin Boyraz and Ahmet Akkuş	Turkey	Submission 741
IN SILICO STUDY THE IMPACT OF ESSENTIAL OILS OF THE LAMIACEAE FAMILY ON CITRUS NEMATODE	Sohayb Bekkal Brikci, Abdelli Imane, Faiçal Hassani, Amina Belhadji, Mimouna Mostari and Meriem Berekci Reguig	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 742
Fabrication and Characterization of Mullite Reinforced CaO Added ZrO ₂ Ceramics	Mehmet Akif Hafizoğlu, Ahmet Akkuş and Tahsin Boyraz	Turkey	Submission 743
Synthesis and Characterization of Limoneen-Based Sulfur Polymer	Ramazan Orhan and Ercan Aydoğmuş	Turkey	Submission 747
Design of Energy Management System Base on lithium-ion Battery	Yusuf Bello Saleh and Prof. Dr. Hasan KÜRÜm	Nigeria, Turkey	Submission 749
The Effect of PHBV-g-MA Compatibilizer on Morphology, Thermal Stability and Fire Properties of Ternary System Based on PHBV/PBS/Halloysite Nanotubes	Nadjet Dehouche, Salima Kennouche, Mustapha Kaci and José-Marie Lopez-Cuesta	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, France	Submission 752

Session 3.12		3 NOV 2021 15:00-16:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Environmental monitoring by big data-based device for intelligent air pollution monitoring	Loubna BOUHACHLAF	Algeria	Submission 754
Çok Ölçekli Eğrilik Sınıflandırmasının CUDA ile Hızlandırılması	Mustafa Oğuz and Sercan Demirci	Turkey	Submission 755
Synthesis of silicoaluminophosphate SAPO-34	Salima Bellatreche and Mohammedabdelkrim Hasnaoui	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 756
Crystal structure, spectroscopic and electrochemical investigation of a new unsymmetrical oxovanadium(IV) complex	Ikram Boucekine and Kamel Ouari	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 757
Maximizing the Yearly Profit of an Indian Nearshore Wind Farm	Prasun Bhattacharjee, Rabin K. Jana and Somenath Bhattacharya	India, India, India	Submission 759
The Role Of Autonomus Vehicule In Sustainable Development	Fatima Ezzahra Khalloufi, Najat Rafalia and Jaafar Abouchabaka	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 764
First principale investigation of half-metallic ferromagnetism in Cr based half-Heusler compound	Bouldiab Yasmine, Terkhi Sabria, Aziz Zoubir, Boudjenane Fatima Zohra and Boudjeltia Mohamed El Amine	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 765
BİLGİSAYAR DESTEKLİ TASARIMIN YARATICILIK VE HEDEF ÇALIŞMA ÜZERİNE ETKİSİ	Havva Demİrpolat	Turkey	Submission 766
Yazılım Güvenlik Açığı Veri Tabanlarının İncelenmesi ve Karşılaştırılması	Hakan KekÜl, Burhan Ergen and Halil Arslan	Turkey	Submission 769
first principle calculations of structural, magneto-electronic, and thermoelectric properties of the new d0 quaternary Heusler compounds RbCaCZ (Z = P, As, Sb).	Slimane Gheriballah, Youssouf Benazzouzi and Abbes Chahed	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 770

Session 3.12		3 NOV 2021 16:00-17:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Derin Öğrenme ve İstatistiksel Modelleme Yöntemiyle Sıcaklık Tahmini ve Karşılaştırılması	Aynur Sevinç and Buket Kaya	Turkey	Submission 771
Marginal Entropy of Square Grid	Bünyamin Şahin and Merve Akbulut	Turkey	Submission 372
Günümüzde ve Gelecekte Eğitim Alanında Kullanılan Yapay Zekâ	Yusuf Uzun, Aleyna Yağmur TÜmtÜrk and Hediye ÖztÜrk	Turkey	Submission 609
Optical characterization of TAPC based thin films	Murat Yildirim	Turkey	Submission 653
An Image Processing Application for Cancer Detection	Gizem Boyraz, Fatma Öztürk and Pinar Kirci	Turkey	Submission 754
Akıllı tarımda sensör uygulaması ile yeni bir yöntem tasarımı	Erdinç Öztürk, Yavuz Çelik and Pinar Kirci	Turkey	Submission 777
WOUND DRESSING FOR MALIGN MELANOMA SKIN CANCER	Hilal Gulsena Nur Akkus, Busra Ece Gunaydin and Cem Bulent Ustundag	Turkey	Submission 233
DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF ARTIFICIAL VESSELS FOR CORONARY ARTERY TREATMENT	Büşra Ece Günaydın, Hilal Gulsena Nur Akkuş and Cem Bülent Üstündağ	Turkey	Submission 235
Kızılırmak Deltası Kıyı Kenar Çizgisindeki zamansal değişimlerin Worldview-2 ve Landsat 7 ETM+ uydu görüntüleri ile belirlenmesi	Erhan Şener	Turkey	Submission 62
Fibonacci Sayı Dizisi ile İlişkili Diferensiyel Denklemler	Ahmed Ibrahim Hayder Alhaidar and Onur Karaoğlu	Turkey	Submission 633

Session 3.13		3 NOV 2021 16:00-17:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Stock Market Analysis with Machine Learning	Mahmut Emir Arslan and Pinar Kirci	Turkey	Submission 775
Synthesis of two analogs of a natural molecule and evaluation of their antioxidant activity	Amina Hammoudi, Amina Tabet Zatla and Mohamed El Amine Dib	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 656
Determination of Rheological Properties and Dispersion Quality of Shear Thickening Fluid	Cenk Yanen, Murat Yavuz Solmaz and Ercan Aydođmuř	Turkey	Submission 400
Spatial and temporal distribution of bycatch fish along the western Black Sea coast of Turkey	Ahmet Mutlu Gzler and Hazel Baytařođlu	Turkey	Submission 719
Influence of Mass Per Unit Area on the Hydraulic Conductivity of GCLs	Fatih Polat, Tuđçe zdamar Kul and Ali Hakan ren	Turkey	Submission 332
Activities of Crocus sativus L.extract against Liver cancer proteins	Hasan Durukan and Burak Tzn	Turkey	Submission 794
Activities of Helichrysum arenarium extract against Lung cancer proteins	Ahmet Demirbař and Burak Tzn	Turkey	Submission 796
Activities of Mentha pulegium extract against breast cancer proteins	Handan Saraç and Burak Tzn	Turkey	Submission 797
Effect of Low-Temperature Aluminizing on 904L Stainless Steel	Emre kszođlu and Kadir Mert Dleker	Turkey	Submission 781
The Analysis of Induced Currents on a Buried Cable in a Multilayer Structure	Baha Kanberođlu and Hilmi Niřancı	Turkey	Submission 772

Session 3.14		3 NOV 2021 17:00-18:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Analysis of Al Hoceima (Morocco) Deformation Caused by a Series of Earthquakes Using Sentinel-1A	Muhire Desire	Morocco	Mail Submission 187
Assessment of Airborne Bacteria and Fungi in Different Home Environments	Seda Naz Sarica, AyŞe Bodur, Özlem Özden Üzmez and Semra MalkoÇ	Turkey	Submission 309
Serotonergic neurons that contribute to copulation activities in Drosophila	Gizem Yuncu, Esmâ Gulsoy, Senanur Balaban and Yasemin Yilmazer	Turkey	Submission 631
Utilizing Deep Learning on System Identification of The Concrete Sound Wall Model	Furkan Günday	Turkey	Submission 181
Utilizing Machine Learning on System Identification of The Border Wall Model	Furkan Günday	Turkey	Submission 182
System Identification of The Bunker Wall Model Using Automated Machine Learning	Sertaç Tuhta	Turkey	Submission 183
System Identification of The Water Channel Model Using Automated Artificial Intelligence	Sertaç Tuhta	Turkey	Submission 184
Betonarme Bir Bina Örneğinde Hızlı Değerlendirme Yöntemi ile İnceleme	Sebnem Metin and Duygu Ozturk	Turkey	Submission 783
Jetson Nano Üzerinde Gerçek Zamanlı Linux Çekirdeği Uygulanması	Salih Palamut, Abdullah Elewi and Erdiñ Avarođlu	Turkey	Submission 507
Premature Birth Detection from EHG signals	Ahmet Sađlam, Ümit Şentürk and İbrahim Yücedađ	Turkey	Submission 746

Session 3.15		3 NOV 2021 09:00-10:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Kombine Derin Öğrenme Tabanlı Epileptik Nöbet Teşhisi	Muhammet Varlı and Hakan Yılmaz	Turkey	Submission 725
Effect of Ultrasonic Extraction Conditions on Bioactive Compounds in Propolis	Büşra Çakır and Nihal Güzel	Turkey	Submission 139
Modifiye MWCNT/CuO Nanokompozitlerinin Optik Özellikleri ve Elektriksel İletkenlikleri Üzerine Non-iyonik Sürfektanın Etkisi	Filiz Boran	Turkey	Submission 117
SnO ₂ Nanoparçacıkların Optik Özellikleri Üzerine Sürfektan Türünün Etkisi	Filiz Boran	Turkey	Submission 427
Biosorptive treatment of Acid Yellow 17 contaminated water using an agricultural waste biomass	Selen Kurtuluş, Sema Çelik and Fatih Sayin	Turkey	Submission 356
Elektrik Akımı Destekli Sinterleme Yöntemi İle Üretilen Stellite 21 Süperalaşımının Sıcak Korozyon Özellikleri	Nuri Ergin, Özkan Özdemir and Ahmet Yiğit Özer	Turkey	Submission 786
Investigation of the inhibition potential on medicinally important enzymes and its chemical composition of Centaurea cadmea subsp. pontica	Zafer Kaya, Rizvan İmamoğlu and Dursun Kisa	Turkey	Submission 474
Non-linear programming problems with quasi strongly E-preinvex function	Askar Hussain	India	Mail Submission-3
The Concept of Antioxidant and Its Importance: An Example of Spices	Hüsnü Kasar and Süleyman Gökmen	Turkey	Submission 434
A Hybrid Approach In The Production Process Of The Etimex Dessert With Orange Sauce: Applications Of Only Gelatin And /Or Gelatin Treated With Infrared Radiation	Hüsnü Kasar and Süleyman Gökmen	Turkey	Submission 473
Kompresör ve türbin palelerinin fişür tasarımlarının parametrik analiz ve sonlu eleman simülasyonları ile incelenmesi	Özgür Poyraz and Nurullah Yandı	Turkey	Submission 119
Extraction and characterisation of a valuable biomaterial from a liquid waste of the Tunisian paper industry	Nawel Tlili and Karim Toumi	Tunisia, Tunisia	Submission 660
Determination of veterinary pharmaceuticals by surface plasmon resonance	Esmâ Sarı	Turkey	Submission 531
Electronic and optical properties of semiconducting monolayer GeC-ohs	Salih Demirci	Turkey	Submission 630

Session 3.16		3 NOV 2021 17:00-18:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Kültürel Mirasın Kullanıcı Merkezli Etkileşimli Deneyimi için Bütünsel Bir Uygulama: 3B Baskı, Artırılmış Gerçeklik ve Web Tabanlı Görselleştirme Kombinasyonu	Ahmet Uslu	Turkey	Submission 629
Detection of DIS Flooding Attacks in IoT Networks Using Machine Learning Methods	Semih Çakır and Nesibe Yalçın	Turkey	Submission 790
Development and Comparison of Skin Cancer Diagnosis Models	Emel Soylu and Rukiye Demir	Turkey	Submission 302
Computing Gauss-Bonnet Theorem of σ -Bezier Curves	Filiz Ertem Kaya	Turkey	Submission 234
Estimate of the structural behavior of reinforced concrete buildings with and without inclined columns	Omair Elshafei El. Mohieldin, Adem Doğangün and Fikret Mehdi	Turkey	Submission 525
Examination of Concentrically Steel Braces on a Steel Structure	Sadrettin Sancioğlu and Serdar Çarbaş	Turkey	Submission 297
The Curvature Property of a Linear Dynamical System	Tuna Bayrakdar and Zahide Ok Bayrakdar	Turkey	Submission 640
Contribution of the coarse aggregate morphology to the workability of concrete “application to Algerian crushed limestone”	Ahmed Boufedah Badissi, Ahmed Beroual, Malika Bentalha, Rafik Meziani and Boubakeur Fettar	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 804
COVID-19 Tespiti için Akciğer BT Görüntülerinin Bölütlenmesi	Buket Kaya and Muhammed Onal	Turkey	Submission 779
VALUATION OF DATE PALM BY-PRODUCTS "PALM JUICE" AS A THERAPEUTIC TOOL FOR NEURODEGENERATIVE DISEASES THROUGH MOLECULAR MODELING	Mimouna Mostari, Imane Abdelli, Faiçal Hassani, Amina Belhadji and Sohayb Bekkal Brikci	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 763
Eğitim-öğretim kurumlarında bilgi yönetim sistemleri: Örnek bir uygulama	Muhammed Hanefi Calp, Resul BÜTÜner and Yusuf Uzun	Turkey	Submission 553

Session 3.17		3 NOV 2021 18:00-19:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
COMPARISON OF ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY TOTAL PHENOLIC, AND TOTAL FLAVONOIDS CONTENT OF BUTANOLIC EXTRACTS FROM HALOXYLON SCOPARIUM AND TRAGANUM NUDATUM	Messaouda Allaoui, Manel Zaoui-Djelloul Daouadji and Abdelkareem Cheriti	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 727
Remote Pre-Diagnosis of Pes Planus and Pes Cavus Using Arch Index Digitally	Kaan Eksen, Safa Serif and Tacha Serif	Turkey, Greece, Turkey	Submission 299
Solid Phase Extraction Methods for Quantification of Trace Elements in Edible Oils	Feyzullah Tokay and Sema Bağdat	Turkey	Submission 527
Liquid-Liquid Extraction of Ni, Fe, Zn and Cu from Plant Derived Oil Samples prior to FAAS Detection	Sema Bağdat and Feyzullah Tokay	Turkey	Submission 528
Importance and Microbial Production of Gamma (γ)-Aminobutyric Acid (GABA) as a Functional Compound in Food Systems	Nilgün Özdemir	Turkey	Submission 711
Konsol Palplanş Duvarların Gömme Derinliklerinin Tahmini	Recep Akan	Turkey	Submission 239
Strength Behavior of Geopolymer Based SIFCON with Different Fibers	Mukhallad Mohammad Mawlod Al-Mashhadani	Turkey	Submission 280
Stress distribution in an elastic rod subjected to initial tip displacement	Mehmet N. Balci	Turkey	Submission 472
Methanation of carbon dioxide using sepiolite supported Nickel catalyts	Tuğba Yarbaş, Nezihe Ayas,	Turkey	Mail Submission 25
Kesikli Akım Elektrobiriktirme Yöntemiyle Üretilen Ni/W-Si ₃ N ₄ Kompozitlerinin Mikroyapı ve Aşınma Özelliklerine Si ₃ N ₄ Konsantrasyonunun Etkisi	Harun GÜL, Nuri Ergün and Mehmet Uysal	Turkey	Submission 785
Mixed Boundary Value Problem for the Bitsadze Equation in a Ring Domain	İlker Gençtürk	Turkey	Submission 465

Session 3.17		3 NOV 2021 18:00-19:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Self-Cleaning Application of TiO ₂ and SiO ₂ Nano Particules on Worsted Fabrics	Neslihan Korkmaz	Turkey	Submission 524
Evaluation of the anticoagulant effect of the phenolic extracts of olive mill wastewater and olive mill pomace	Zakia Gueboudji, Kenza Kadi and Kamel Nagaz	Algeria, Algeria, tunusia	Submission 153
Intercalation of montmorillonite clay for the Preparation of nanocomposites	Imene Toumi, Fatiha Bessaha and Abdeghani Benyoucef	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 628
EKSENEL BASINÇ YÜKÜ ALTINDA FARKLI EBATLI BETON KÜP NUMUNELERDE BOYUT ETKİSİNİN İNCELENMESİ	Hakan Aydın	Turkey	Submission 433
Establishment of Case Number Inventory of Flood Disasters in Turkey on Basin Basis	Yıldırım Bayazıt	Turkey	Submission 414
Microplastic Pollution and Hydrodynamic Modeling in Rivers	Olca Gülçiçek Uysal	Turkey	Submission 543
Su Ortamından Mikroplastik Giderimine Genel Bakış	Olca Gülçiçek Uysal	Turkey	Submission 645
Characterizations of 12-tungstophosphoric acid metal salts nano particles synthesized by ultrasound	Elif Akbay and Mert Can Ertaş	Turkey	Submission 761
Turkish Traffic Sign Recognition: Comparison of Training Step Numbers and Lighting Conditions	Kaan Kocakanat and Tacha Serif	Turkey	Submission 335
Eğitim Amaçlı 8051 Tabanlı Deney Seti Tasarımı, Gerçeklenmesi ve Uygulamaları	Ersagun Kürşat Yaylacı, Ali Buğra Çetin and Ahmet Serhat Aykılıç	Turkey	Submission 523
Self-Cleaning Application of TiO ₂ and SiO ₂ Nano Particules on Worsted Fabrics	Neslihan Korkmaz	Turkey	Submission 524
Removal of Methylene Blue from Aqueous Solutions with Fly Ash Based Geopolymer Foam	Evren Arıöz and Gözde Bahar Büke	Turkey	Submission 789
Length-Weight Relationship and Condition Factor of Transcaucasian spirin <i>Alburnoides fasciatus</i> (Nordmann, 1840) from the lower Çoruh river basin (NE Turkey)	Tuncay Yeşilçiçek	Turkey	Submission 728
Investigation of Gain Enhancement in Microstrip Antenna Structure in Pathological Tissue Samples	Rabia Toprak, Seyfettin Sinan Gültekin and Dilek Uzer	Turkey	Submission 340
Investigation of Normalization Values of Microstrip Antenna Structure and S-Parameters in Pathological Tissue Samples	Rabia Toprak, Seyfettin Sinan Gültekin and Dilek Uzer	Turkey	Submission 341

Kuzuluk (Sakarya) Bölgesindeki Eosen Yaşlı Tüflerde Gözlenen Cu-Zn Cevherleşmesinin Jeokimyası ve CBS Ortamında Analizi	Cihan Yaçın, Mustafa Kumral, Zübeyde Buket Aydın, Ceren Korkmaz, Alişan Gürsoy, Onur Aksoy	Turkey	Mail Submission 15
Nanoparçacık Takviyeli Epoksi Nanokompozitlerin Eğilme Davranışları	Kazım Tolga Çınar and Mürsel Ekrem	Turkey	Submission 784
3D Printed Horn Antenna for Near field ISAR Imaging Applications	Huseyin Duysak, Enes Yigit and Levent Seyfi	Turkey	Submission 729
Silo Tahıl Analizinde Makine Öğrenmesi Destekli Radar Sistemleri Tasarımı	İrem ÖZSOY, Gizem ÖZDEMİR, Umut ÖZKAYA, Enes YİĞİT, Hüseyin DUYSAK	Turkey	Mail Submission 187
Friction and Wear Properties of High Concentration Polyacrylamide/Alginate Hydrogels	Yusuf Kanca	Turkey	Submission 803

Session 1.19		1 NOV 2021 20:00-21:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Comparative online meal delivery analysis for before and after the Covid-19 pandemic	Vanda Chhiev	Cambodia	Mail Submission 46
Performance evaluation of Absortive and Dynamic Capacitors	Raymond M. Ramos	Philippines	Mail Submission 47
Analysis of factors affecting service usage in mobile banking (Indonesia example)	Budi Septiawan	Indonesia	Mail Submission 48
A review on Crowdfunding and Financial Inclusion	Amina Slimani	Morocco	Mail Submission 49
Implementation of an experiential teaching model for Increasing Reading	Phananoi Rotchu	Thailand	Mail Submission 50
Discount Price Segmentation Based On Area Of Sales Using Cluster Analysis For Automotive Dealers In Indonesia	Krisha Adhya Nirwana	Indonesia	Mail Submission 51
Cluster analysis to increase sales rates of automotive dealers	Mufti Afif	Indonesia	Mail Submission 52
A slow learning new method for sewing program	Norain Abdul Rashid	Malaysia	Mail Submission 53
In Word Extraction Strategies on Vietnamese students	Thu Nguyen Thi Anh	Vietnam	Mail Submission 54
Accounting Calculations And Explanations On The Basis Of Local Government	Neilson Anak Teruki	Malaysia	Mail Submission 55
The effect of product logo design on consumer behavior	Hilman Fauzi	Indonesia	Mail Submission 56

Session 1.20		1 NOV 2021 20:00-21:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Formation of coalition unity to form an effective government (Indonesia Example)	Ahmad Muhibbin	Indonesia	Mail Submission 57
Seasonal characteristics of Upper Jebba Basin Catfish	Adelakun KM.	Nigeria	Mail Submission 58
Contribution of sweet melon production to Nigerian economy	Omorogbe I.	Nigeria	Mail Submission 59
Effect of wood chip bioreactors on nitrate removal in soil	Shakeel Ahmad Bhat	India	Mail Submission 60
Reducing the impact of climate change with the sustainable management of rainforests	Trond Norheim	Denmark	Mail Submission 61
The effect of industrial wastes on cattle operations in Indonesia	Diffah Hanim	Indonesia	Mail Submission 62
An Improved Learning Algorithm For Nonlinear Channel Equalization	Zohra Zerdoumi, Khansa Bdirina, Ghania Zidani And Djamel Benatia	Algeria	Submission 806
The impact of education transitions on developing countries	Aniket Srivastava	India	Mail Submission 63
Mizorami Food and pulses dynamics in India	Paul Lalremsang	India	Mail Submission 64
The effect of foliar feeding on bean production (Kenya Example)	Boniface Mwami	Kenya	Mail Submission 65
Implementation of Concentration Effect Simulation	Michael David	Malaysia	Mail Submission 66

Session 1.21		1 NOV 2021 21:00-22:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Using the Modified Hummer Method in Graphene Oxide Synthesis	Sakinah Md Tia	Malaysia	Mail Submission 67
non-contact conductivity in different metabolites	Thang Lee Yen	Malaysia	Mail Submission 68
Gamma alumina obtained from canoe oil with Na modification	Abdu Muhammad Bello	Nigeria	Mail Submission 69
Bleaching of different oils to obtain clay-rich soil	Abdu Muhammad Bello	Nigeria	Mail Submission 70
Surface modification of doped nanotubes under visible light	Naimat Abimbola Eleburuke	Malaysia	Mail Submission 71
Analysis of awareness of arsenic element in water	Muhammad Khalis Abdul Karim	Malaysia	Mail Submission 72
Wild Bootstrap effect in linear regression model	Mohammad Sabry Abo Al-Mash	Iran	Mail Submission 73
Performance of different estimators in Multiple regression model	Bello Abdulkadir Rasheed	Iraq	Mail Submission 74
Non-Linear Tension plate in Casson fluid	Sharidan Shafie	Saudi Arabia	Mail Submission 76
Different approaches to risk analysis optimization	Zuhaimy Ismail	Malaysia	Mail Submission 77
Use of different modes in discrete and nonlinear Schrödinger equation	Bakhram Umarov	Malaysia	Mail Submission 78

Session 1.22		1 NOV 2021 21:00-22:00	
Title	Author Names	Country	Submission Id
The effect of the Garch Model in the US dollar and gold market	Norazlina Binti Ismail	Malaysia	Mail Submission 79
Subgroup effect theory in finite groups	Ahmad Erfanian	Iran	Mail Submission 80
Solving limited Robin problems with a generalized Neumann Kernel by using Lts estimator	Mukhiddin I. Muminov	Malaysia	Mail Submission 81
Solving Limited Robin Problems With A Generalized Neumann Kernel-Robust Wild Bootstrap By Using Lts Estimator	Seyed Ehsan Saffari	Iran	Mail Submission 82
Wetland system built using model plant species	Mohd Razman Salim	Malaysia	Mail Submission 83
Pressure wave propagation of a two-phase fluid in an Inclined Pipe	Jibrin Mbaya Helma	Malaysia	Mail Submission 84
Radon amount in drinking water and health risk (Example of Juban, Yemen)	Wedad Ali Abdurabu	Yemen	Mail Submission 85
The use of Thermal Neutron reflection technique in the determination of the amount of hydrogen in agriculture	Habu Tela Abba	Nigeria	Mail Submission 86
Effect of Co-60 Gamma Ray on Thermoluminescence Properties of Lithium Borate Glass	H.Wagiran	Iraq	Mail Submission 87
Determination of the type and amount of volatile compounds by Long Optical Path Infrared Spectroscopy technique	Yusof Munajat	Malaysia	Mail Submission 88
Luminescent effect of Magnesium Sulphoborate Doped Phosphorus in white led design	Aliyu M. Aliyu	Nigeria	Mail Submission 89

Session 1.22		1 NOV 2021 22:00-23:00	
Title	Author Names	Country	Submission Id
Ligand field parameters of gold particle doped Tellurite	S.K. Ghoshal	Malaysia	Mail Submission 90
Providing Food Characterization Using Xrf Spectrometer	Habu Tela Abba	Nigeria	Mail Submission 91
Determination of luminance properties of Doped TeO ₂ -Na ₂ O Glasses	SAMAN Q. MAWLUD,	Iraq	Mail Submission 92
The effect of different irradiation techniques on the Properties of Doped Lithium Borate Glass	Husin Wagiran	Malaysia	Mail Submission 93
Temperature and time adjustment of copper-doped Lithium Magnesium Borate Glass	Husin Wagiran	Malaysia	Mail Submission 94
Radiation level measurement in radiological operations	Khatijah Abu Bakar	Malaysia	Mail Submission 95
Using the finite element method in resonator simulation	Enrique Iborra,	Spain	Mail Submission 96
Evaluation of Chest X-Ray images for differential diagnosis	Suhairul Hashim	Malaysia	Mail Submission 97
Structure and Absorbance of Fluoro-Chloro-Tellurite Glass	S.K. Ghoshal	Malaysia	Mail Submission 98
Effect of reflecting radar on antenna polarization	S.K. Ghoshal	Malaysia	Mail Submission 99
Effect of Calcium Fluoride Concentration in Zinc-Telluride Glass	S.K. Ghoshal	Malaysia	Mail Submission 100

Session 1.23		1 NOV 2021 22:00-23:00	
Title	Author Names	Country	Submission Id
Surface texture mapping with Terahertz Thermal tomography	Muhamad Hamdi	Indonesia	Mail Submission 101
Radiological impact research at Lahad Datu	Noor Zati Hanı Abu Hamfah	Malaysia	Mail Submission 102
Distribution of radiological risk caused by Nuclear Accident in Mersing, Malaysia	Nor Afifah Basrı	Malaysia	Mail Submission 103
Radiological Evaluation of Johor, Malaysia	Nor Afifah Basrı	Malaysia	Mail Submission 104
Experimental simulation of Hollow Beam Formation in Multifibre Mode	Saman Q. Mawlud	Iraq	Mail Submission 105
Compressive strength of Ground Slag Mixed Geopolymer Mortar under curing conditions	Mohd Azreen Mohd Ariffin	Malaysia	Mail Submission 106
An Analysis on Critical Elements in Construction Projects	Alı Mohammed Alı	Malaysia	Mail Submission 107
A novel Hyper-Heuristic Clustering Algorithm	Nıayesh Gharaei	Malaysia	Mail Submission 108
Environmental pollution and prevention activities in Nigeria	Alıyu Hassan Ibrahim	Nigeria	Mail Submission 109
Correlation study for different physiological parameters in rice cultivation	Muhammad Arshad Javed	Malaysia	Mail Submission 110
Load and voltage analysis of high voltage Photovoltaic Grid	Martino Adısuwono	Malaysia	Mail Submission 111

Session 2.24		1 NOV 2021 21:00-22:00	
Title	Author Names	Country	Submission Id
An analysis on increasing fruit shelf life and quality of Plastic Packaging Applications	Soesiladi Esti Widodo	Indonesia	Mail Submission 113
A preliminary study on Algal Immobilization of Zeolite 13X	Rabitah Zakaria	Malaysia	Mail Submission 114
Obtaining bioethanol with pretreatment support of Water Hyacinth	Mohd Yusof Harun	Malaysia	Mail Submission 115
Protein Hydrolyzate supplemented by Soldier Fly Larvae in the concept of biotransformation	Muhammad Yusuf Abduh	Indonesia	Mail Submission 116
Use of Imidazolium Based Ionic Liquids for the purpose of EPA and DHA Extraction from Microalgae	Siti Aslina Hussain	Malaysia	Mail Submission 117
Mechanical strengths of Polylactic Acid / Polypropylene Carbonate (PLA/PPC) Mixtures after Solvent Casting	Sharifah Imihezri Syed Shahrudin	Malaysia	Mail Submission 118
Effect of stingless beekeeping on coffee production	Muhammad Yusuf Abduh	Indonesia	Mail Submission 119
Biocellulose-based biocomposite characterization for hydrogen gas sensor design	Faizah Md Yasin	Malaysia	Mail Submission 120
Monitoring the characterization of crude methanol extract with different spectroscopy techniques	Khalid Hamid Musa	Saudi Arabia	Mail Submission 121
The effect of Pineapple fiber obtained as a result of hydrolysis process on Polylactic acid composite	Sarah Amalina Adli	Malaysia	Mail Submission 122
Measurement of E. coli O157:H7 using scavenging voltammetry in different water types	Wan Wardatul Amani Wan Salim	Malaysia	Mail Submission 123

Session 2.25		1 NOV 2021 21:00-22:00	
Title	Author Names	Country	Submission Id
A new optimization technique for enhancing the Amino functionality of Magnetic Nanoparticles	Nor Fadhillah Mohamed Azmin	Malaysia	Mail Submission 124
Investigation of Physicochemical Properties of Struvite Crystals obtained in mills	Loh Soh Kheang	Malaysia	Mail Submission 125
Analysis of Cold Active Protease on the Antarctic continent	Jerzy Smykla	Poland	Mail Submission 126
The use of basil oil to increase yield in plant breeding	Yasmin A. A. Aburigal	Sudan	Mail Submission 127
Transforming Fish Gelatin Hydrolysates into Nanoparticles as Drug Carrier	Irwandi Jaswir	Malaysia	Mail Submission 128
Conversion of Fish Gelatin Hydrolysates into nanoparticles within the scope of pharmaceutical production	Zaki Zainuddin	Malaysia	Mail Submission 129
3-D modeling of thyroid cancer	Munira Shahbuddin	Malaysia	Mail Submission 130
Investigation of boron adsorption in date seed	Mohamed Elwathig Saeed Mirghani	Malaysia	Mail Submission 131
Effects of different ambient conditions and temperature on shelf life of 'Callina' Papaya	Suskandini R. Dirmawati	Indonesia	Mail Submission 132
Comparison of different culture media for lutein production	Mokhzanni Mustapa	Malaysia	Mail Submission 133
Effect of Moringa Oleifera Seeds on Boron Adsorption in seawater	Mani Malam Ahmad	Malaysia	Mail Submission 134

Session 2.26		1 NOV 2021 22:00-23:00	
Title	Author Names	Country	Submission Id
Removal of nutrients in wastewater by <i>Chlorella</i> sp	Fadi I.A. Alqedra	Malaysia	Mail Submission 135
New coagulant methods in wastewater treatment	Rahayu Sulaiman	Malaysia	Mail Submission 136
Activation and optimization of Durian Shell by Zinc biosorption in aqueous medium	Mohammed Saedi Jami	Malaysia	Mail Submission 137
Auto-encoder based biometric encryption system	Boris Assanovich	Belarus	Mail Submission 138
Cognitive activity effect of different reality applications on the aging population	M.V. Gómez-Gómez	Germany	Mail Submission 139
Supporting motor skills in the elderly	Veronika Kotradyová	Slovakia	Mail Submission 140
A new ICT healthcare solution taking into account user requirements	R. Martínez	Spain	Mail Submission 141
Psychological recommendations for all age groups	Dumitru MICUSHA	Moldova	Mail Submission 142
Multi-featured algorithm developed on activity recognition	Angelica Poli	Italy	Mail Submission 143
Good position detection to use the inertial motion unit at high efficiency	Zahra Rahemtulla	UK	Mail Submission 144
Common area construction to cover different age groups	Willeke van Staalduinen	Netherlands	Mail Submission 145

Session 2.27		1 NOV 2021 22:00-23:00	
Title	Author Names	Country	Submission Id
Mobile application for Retirement home residents	Fernando Terroso-Saenz	Spain	Mail Submission 146
The impact of the Covid-19 outbreak on online catering services	Tetsou Yai	Japan	Mail Submission 147
Increasing the absorption capacity in industry positioning	Raymond M. Ramos	Philippines	Mail Submission 148
The effect of mobile banking services on user behavior	Rizal Edy Halim	Philippines	Mail Submission 149
A systematic literature review in crowdfunding	Mustapha Ziky	Morocco	Mail Submission 150
A model to increase the communication skills of experiential learning-based undergraduate students	Phananoi Rotchu	Thailand	Mail Submission 151
Discounted price segmentation by performing cluster analysis in the sales area of auto dealers	Athor Subroto	Indonesia	Mail Submission 152
Shariah practices in the institution of monetary foundations	Manggini Tejokusumo	Indonesia	Mail Submission 153
Interactive module for slow learners in sewing	Syafiqah Amin	Malaysia	Mail Submission 154
Vietnamese PFL Learners' learning strategies in word extraction	Thu Nguyen Thi Anh1	Malaysia	Mail Submission 155
Accounting Disclosure Reasons for Management	Neilson Anak Teruki	Malaysia	Mail Submission 156

Session 2.28		1 NOV 2021 22:00-23:00	
Title	Author Names	Country	Submission Id
Examining the effect of product logos in neuromarkets	Denta Rahmadani	Indonesia	Mail Submission 157
The urgency of the coalition government for the formation of an effective government in Indonesia	Abdillah Nugroho	Indonesia	Mail Submission 158
Using the digital world to make sustainable development effective in Africa	Olajide Kufoniyi	Nigeria	Mail Submission 159
Load Balancing Methods on Geographic Information Service	Fengtao	China	Mail Submission 160
Video-based 3D Object location and Motion Simulation	Changshun Guo	China	Mail Submission 161
Digital data flow in geological surveys	Stephen Thorpe	Uk	Mail Submission 162
Research On 3D Visualization Of Typhoon Satellite Cloud Image Based On Digital Earth	Jin Qinwen	China	Mail Submission 163
Automatic Recognition Of Chinese Regional Landform Based On Slope Spectrum Method	L1 Chenrui	China	Mail Submission 164
Multi-Temporal Landsat Images analysis with machine learning-based Support vector machine	Samy Ismail Elmahdy	Egypt	Mail Submission 165
New terrain change and detection model	Dong Yu	China	Mail Submission 166
Analysis of land floods and vulnerabilities in Nigeria	O. J. Taiwo	Nigeria	Mail Submission 167

Session 2.29		1 NOV 2021 22:00-23:00	
Title	Author Names	Country	Submission Id
Using the Digital World for sustainable collaborations	Luis Perez-Mora	Australia	Mail Submission 168
Use of data fusion for crop productivity analysis	Rui Sun	China	Mail Submission 169
Modeling of port trade competition with Data mining method	Naixia Mou	China	Mail Submission 170
Structure and features of the digital world	Hongyi Yuan	China	Mail Submission 171
Large-scale mapping and operational-based terrain classification at 30m resolution	Xiao Zhang	China	Mail Submission 172
Harmonized information service	Thomas Kemper	Italy	Mail Submission 173
Bioinformatic Analysis Of Human Collagen Sequence Mutations On Osteogenesis Imperfecta	Esma Eryilmaz Doğan and Gülsüm Tıraş	Turkey	Submission 798
Control and command strategy for a double star induction motor	Basma Benbouya and Hocine Cheghib	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 619
Effect on the isolation of plant cellulose from Rotten Banana Skin and Sugar Cane Baguette	Parveen Jamal	Malaysia	Mail Submission 174
Testing Mycelial Fungi Fermentation as Mycocoagulant	Abdullah Al Mamun	Malaysia	Mail Submission 175
Effect of Lysozyme-Loaded Zinc Oxide Nanospheres in Antimicrobial Treatment	Husna Ahmad Tajuddin	Malaysia	Mail Submission 176

Session 2.30		1 NOV 2021 22:00-23:00	
Title	Author Names	Country	Submission Id
Annual germination behavior of red pepper	Zulaikha Sarobo	Malaysia	Mail Submission 177
Effects of iron toxins on rice germination	Nusrat Jahan	Malaysia	Mail Submission 178
Photovoltaic cell placement in integrated building structures	Enegbuma, W.	Nigeria	Mail Submission 179
The impact of institutions on sustainable development in Nigeria	Abdullahi, A.	Nigeria	Mail Submission 180
Analysis of Tissue Characteristics of Adipose Slaughtered in Halal Meat	Nor Azwani Mohd Shukri	Malaysia	Mail Submission 181
Degradation stages of Polychlorinated Biphenyls in Landfill Leachate	Noor Faizul Hadry Nordin	Malaysia	Mail Submission 182
An analysis on Printing Ink in Forensic Applications	Naji Arafat Mahat	Malaysia	Mail Submission 183
Use of Pla/Alg Nanocomposites in Industrial Packaging	Azlin Suhaida Azmi	Malaysia	Mail Submission 184